

**Learning from conditionals: A critical
assessment of recent proposals**

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1 Introduction

An agent who learns the indicative conditional 'If A , then B .' should update her credences P over A and B . The central question is how should the update be. The learning is typically modelled in a probabilistic framework which allows to consider non-strict conditionals and partial beliefs and to apply the reasoning from Bayesian epistemology. It is generally thought that if the conditional is non-strict, the problem is underdetermined by Bayesian norms. In this article we show that this is actually not the case. There is no need/space for additional principles. Jeffrey conditionalisation determines completely the update. The update is appropriate for the Judy Benjamin problem and for the more general Lena the scientist problem.

We start by shortly introducing updating by Bayesian conditionalisation in section 2. In section 3 we extend and correct the characterisation obtained by Eva et al. (2020) for updating by minimizing f -divergences. The result will help us benchmark Jeffrey conditionalisation afterwards. In section 4 we introduce updating by Jeffrey conditionalisation along with some basic results. In the following two sections we apply Jeffrey conditionalisation to test case problems: Judy Benjamin (in section 5) and Lena the scientist (in section 6). In section 7 we present some additional results on updating by Jeffrey conditionalisation. The main result there is that learning the non-strict conditional 'If A , then B .' and updating by Jeffrey conditionalisation yields the same update as learning (the non-strict conditional) 'If $\neg B$, then $\neg A$.' and updating by Jeffrey conditionalisation.

2 Updating by Bayesian conditionalisation

Let A and B be propositional variables (in italic script). The propositional variable A attains the values A and $\neg A$ (in roman script) and the propositional variable B attains the values B and $\neg B$ (in roman script). We assume that the a priori credences of an agent is represented by a probability distribution P which is defined over the propositional variables A and B . Let P be parametrized as follows: $P(A) = a$, $P(B|A) = p$ and $P(B|\neg A) = q$ where $0 < a, p, q < 1$. This is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} P(A \wedge B) &= ap & , & & P(A \wedge \neg B) &= a\bar{p} \\ P(\neg A \wedge B) &= \bar{a}q & , & & P(\neg A \wedge \neg B) &= \bar{a}\bar{q} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where the bar over the parameter \bar{x} is short for $1 - x$.

Assume that an agent learns¹ 'If A , then B .' and imposes $P_1^*(B|A) = p' = 1$ where P_1^* denote the probability distribution which represents the a posteriori credences of the

¹from a fully reliable information source and there is no possibility to disable

agent. Since

$$1 = P_1^*(B|A) = \frac{P_1^*(A \wedge B)}{P_1^*(A)}$$

i. e. $P_1^*(A) = P_1^*(A \wedge B)$ but $P_1^*(A) = P_1^*(A \wedge B) + P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B)$, learning $P_1^*(B|A) = p' = 1$ is equivalent to learning

$$P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B) = 0$$

respectively to learning

$$P_1^*(\neg A \vee B) = 1.$$

Since A and B are propositional variables the expression $\neg A \vee B$ is a propositional variable and hence we can determine the a posteriori probability distribution P_1^* by Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$, i. e.

$$P_1^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee B)$$

This implies that

$$\begin{aligned} P_1^*(A \wedge B) &= \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}} & , & & P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B) &= 0 \\ P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B) &= \frac{\bar{a}q}{ap + \bar{a}} & , & & P_1^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) &= \frac{\bar{a}\bar{q}}{ap + \bar{a}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

c. f. Eva et al. (2020, p. 466, 497). It is well known that the probability of A decreases, i. e. $P_1^*(A) < P(A)$, and that the probability of B increases, i. e. $P_1^*(B) > P(B)$, c. f. Eva et al. (2020, p. 467) and Popper and Miller (1983).

Next, consider the case $p' = 0$. Let P_0^* denote the probability distribution which represents the a posteriori credences of an agent. The agent imposes $P_0^*(B|A) = p' = 0$. Since

$$0 = P_0^*(B|A) = \frac{P_0^*(A \wedge B)}{P_0^*(A)}$$

i. e. $P_0^*(A \wedge B) = 0$. The latter is equivalent to

$$P_0^*(\neg A \vee \neg B) = 1.$$

Hence, the agent determines P_0^* by Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$, i. e. $P_0^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee \neg B)$. Note, $P(\neg A \vee \neg B) = a\bar{p} + \bar{a}$ and evaluation of the conditional probability $P(\cdot | \neg A \vee \neg B)$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} P_0^*(A \wedge B) &= 0 & , & & P_0^*(A \wedge \neg B) &= \frac{a\bar{p}}{a\bar{p} + \bar{a}} \\ P_0^*(\neg A \wedge B) &= \frac{\bar{a}q}{a\bar{p} + \bar{a}} & , & & P_0^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) &= \frac{\bar{a}\bar{q}}{a\bar{p} + \bar{a}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

3 Updating by minimizing f -divergences

Minimizing f -divergences is an well-known approach to determine the update if the learnt conditional is non-strict, i. e. if the agent imposes $Q(B|A) = p' < 1$ (with $0 < p'$) where Q denotes the a posteriori probability distribution which represents the a posteriori credences of the agent. The approach was recently formulized and generalized by Eva et al. (2020). They showed that there are formulas to determine the a posteriori probability distribution Q . More precisely, if Q is parametrized in the following way $Q(A) = a'$, $Q(B|A) = p'$ and $Q(B|\neg A) = q'$, $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$, or equivalently if

$$\begin{aligned} Q(A, B) &= a'p' & , & & Q(A, \neg B) &= a'\bar{p}' \\ Q(\neg A, B) &= \bar{a}'q' & , & & Q(\neg A, \neg B) &= \bar{a}'\bar{q}' \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

and the f -divergence between Q and P is defined by

$$F_f := \sum_{i=1}^4 P(S_i) f\left(\frac{Q(S_i)}{P(S_i)}\right)$$

where $S_1 := A \wedge B$, $S_2 := A \wedge \neg B$, $S_3 := \neg A \wedge B$ and $S_4 := \neg A \wedge \neg B$ and f is a convex function such that $f(1) = 0$, then minimizing the f -divergence between Q and P implies that

$$q' = q \quad \text{and} \quad a' = \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l} \quad (5)$$

where the value of the likelihood ratio l depends on the particular f -divergence:

$$\begin{aligned} l_{IKL} &= 1 & , & & l_{KL} &= \left(\frac{p'}{p}\right)^{p'} \left(\frac{\bar{p}'}{\bar{p}}\right)^{\bar{p}'} \\ l_H &= \frac{1}{\left(\sqrt{pp'} + \sqrt{\bar{p}\bar{p}'}\right)^2} & , & & l_{\chi^2} &= \frac{p'^2}{p} + \frac{\bar{p}'^2}{\bar{p}} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

c. f. Eva et al. (2020, Proposition 4, p. 481).

Note, IKL refers to the inverse Kullback-Leibler divergence ($f(x) = x \log x$), KL refers to the Kullback-Leibler divergence ($f(x) = -\log x$), H refers to the Hellinger distance ($f(x) = (1 - \sqrt{x})^2$) and χ^2 refers to χ^2 -divergence ($f(x) = (x - 1)^2$).

The result is quite general since it applies to any f -divergence and to any $p' \in (p, 1)$ (Eva et al., 2020, c. f. Proposition 4, p. 481). The condition $p' \in (p, 1)$ however rises the question whether it is possible to extend the characterisation to $p' = 1$ and to $p' \in [0, p]$. It looks like that there are two lines of theories: one for learning strict conditionals, i. e. for $p' = 1$ respectively $p' = 0$ (see section 2), and one for learning non-strict conditionals, i. e. for $0 < p' < 1$. Our intuition is that there should be a smooth transition and in particular

that there is no jump from $p' < 1$ to $p' = 1$ respectively from $p' > 0$ to $p' = 0$. Our intuition is that Q should be very similar in the cases $p' = 0.99$ and $p' = 1$. A minimum to capture these intuitions is to require that Q should be a continuous function² of p' at $p' = 1$ respectively at $p' = 0$. Furthermore, we have the intuition that Q should be not only a continuous function of p' at $p' = 1$ and at $p' = 0$ but for all $p' \in [0, 1]$. This rises the question whether minimizing f -divergences determines Q such that Q is a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$ and coincides with Bayesian conditionalisation if $p' = 1$ respectively if $p' = 0$.

The f -divergence between Q and P is given by

$$F_f = ap f\left(\frac{a'p'}{ap}\right) + a\bar{p} f\left(\frac{a'\bar{p}'}{a\bar{p}}\right) + \bar{a}q f\left(\frac{\bar{a}'q'}{\bar{a}q}\right) + \bar{a}\bar{q} f\left(\frac{\bar{a}'\bar{q}'}{\bar{a}\bar{q}}\right).$$

If we want to consider the minimization of F_f if $p' = 0$ respectively if $p' = 1$, then f must be defined on \mathbb{R}_0^+ (and not only on \mathbb{R}^+). Note

$$\begin{aligned} f_H : \mathbb{R}_0^+ &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} & , & & f_H(x) &= (1 - \sqrt{x})^2 \\ f_{\chi^2} : \mathbb{R}_0^+ &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} & , & & f_{\chi^2}(x) &= (x - 1)^2 \\ f_{KL} : \mathbb{R}_0^+ &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} & , & & f_{KL}(x) &= \begin{cases} x \log x & , \text{ if } x > 0 \\ 0 & , \text{ if } x = 0 \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

where $f_{KL}(0) := \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x \log x = 0$. The inverse Kullback-Leibler divergence is not defined at $x = 0$

$$f_{IKL} : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad , \quad f_{IKL}(x) = -\log x.$$

We may however define

$$f_{IKL}(0) := \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} f_{IKL}(x) = +\infty$$

and extend \mathbb{R} formally by $\{+\infty\}$.

Note, since f is assumed to be convex, f is twice differentiable on \mathbb{R}^+ . We define $f'(0) :=$

²We call Q a continuous function of p' if $Q(A, B)$, $Q(A, \neg B)$, $Q(\neg A, B)$ and $Q(\neg A, \neg B)$ are continuous functions of p' .

$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} f'(x)$ and extend \mathbb{R} by $\{\pm\infty\}$ if necessary:

$$\begin{aligned}
f'_H : \mathbb{R}_0^+ &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{-\infty\} \quad , \quad f'_H(x) = \begin{cases} 1 - 1/\sqrt{x} & , \text{if } x > 0 \\ -\infty & , \text{if } x = 0 \end{cases} \\
f'_{\chi^2} : \mathbb{R}_0^+ &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad , \quad f'_{\chi^2}(x) = 2(x - 1) \\
f'_{KL} : \mathbb{R}_0^+ &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{-\infty\} \quad , \quad f'_{KL}(x) = \begin{cases} \log x + 1 & , \text{if } x > 0 \\ -\infty & , \text{if } x = 0 \end{cases} \\
f'_{IKL} : \mathbb{R}_0^+ &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{-\infty\} \quad , \quad f'_{IKL}(x) = \begin{cases} -1/x & , \text{if } x > 0 \\ -\infty & , \text{if } x = 0 \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

We intend to show that the update obtained by minimizing f -divergences coincides with Bayesian conditionalisation if $p' = 0$ respectively if $p' = 1$. For this purpose we have to sort out some f -divergences. We will need to require that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'(x) = 0 \quad (7)$$

Note,

$$\begin{aligned}
x f'_{KL}(x) &= x \log x + x \quad , \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'_{KL}(x) = 0 \\
x f'_H(x) &= \sqrt{x} (\sqrt{x} - 1) \quad , \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'_H(x) = 0 \\
x f'_{\chi^2}(x) &= 2x (x - 1) \quad , \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'_{\chi^2}(x) = 0
\end{aligned}$$

however

$$x f'_{IKL}(x) = -1 \quad , \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'_{IKL}(x) = -1. \quad (8)$$

Before we state the result, let us commence with two lemmas.

Lemma 1. *Let P, P_0^*, P_1^* and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . Let*

P be parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

P_0^ be defined by Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$, i. e. $P_0^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee \neg B)$,*

P_1^ be defined by Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$, i. e. $P_1^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee B)$,*

Q be parametrized according to eqs. (4) with parameters $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$.

If $a' := a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot l)$, where $l \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$, and $q' = q$, then

$$Q = \begin{cases} P_0^* & \text{if } p' = 0 \text{ and } l = 1/\bar{p} \\ P & \text{if } p' = p \text{ and } l = 1 \\ P_1^* & \text{if } p' = 1 \text{ and } l = 1/p \end{cases}$$

The proof of the lemma is given in section A.1.

Lemma 2. Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . Let

P be parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

Q be parametrized according to eqs. (4) with parameters $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$.

$q' = q$ and $a' := a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot l)$, where $l = l(p') \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$

Iff l is a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$, then Q is a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$.

The proof of the lemma is given in section A.2.

Observe, the likelihood ratios l_{IKL} , l_{KL} , l_H and l_{χ^2} are continuous functions of p' on $[0, 1]$, c. f. equations (6). For $p' = p$, we obtain

$$l_{KL}(p) = l_H(p) = l_{\chi^2}(p) = l_{IKL}(p) = 1 \quad (9)$$

and for $p' = 0$ respectively $p' = 1$ we obtain

$$l_{KL}(0) = l_H(0) = l_{\chi^2}(0) = \frac{1}{\bar{p}} \quad (10)$$

$$l_{KL}(1) = l_H(1) = l_{\chi^2}(1) = \frac{1}{p} \quad (11)$$

but

$$l_{IKL}(0) = l_{IKL}(1) = 1. \quad (12)$$

Next, we state two propositions which extend proposition 4 of Eva et al. (2020) to $p' \in [0, 1]$: The first one is only valid for f -divergences which satisfy the condition (7). The second proposition applies only to the IKL-divergence.

Proposition 1. Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . Let

P be parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

Q be parametrized according to eqs. (4) with parameters $0 < a' < 1$ and $0 \leq p', q' \leq 1$,

$f : \mathbb{R}_0^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denote a strictly convex function with $f(1) = 0$, $f(0) := \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} f(x)$ and

$f'(0) := \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} f'(x)$.

If f satisfies $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'(x) = 0$, then minimizing the f -divergence F_f between Q and P with respect to a' and q' implies that

$$(i) \quad q' = q \quad \text{and} \quad a' = \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l}$$

where $l : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ and $l(0) = 1/\bar{p}$, $l(p) = 1$ and $l(1) = 1/p$. The likelihood ratio depends on $(0, p)$ and on $(p, 1)$ on the particular f -divergence:

$$l_{KL} = \left(\frac{p'}{p}\right)^{p'} \left(\frac{\bar{p}'}{\bar{p}}\right)^{\bar{p}'}, \quad (13)$$

$$l_H = \frac{1}{\left(\sqrt{pp'} + \sqrt{\bar{p}\bar{p}'}\right)^2}, \quad l_{\chi^2} = \frac{p'^2}{p} + \frac{\bar{p}'^2}{\bar{p}}$$

(ii) Q is a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$.

$$(iii) \quad Q = \begin{cases} P_0^* & \text{if } p' = 0 \\ P & \text{if } p' = p \\ P_1^* & \text{if } p' = 1 \end{cases}$$

where $P_0^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee \neg B)$ and $P_1^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee B)$.

(iv) $Q(B) = P(B) + [(p' - p) - \bar{a}(l - 1)(p - q)] \cdot Q(A)$ can be smaller than, equal to, or larger than $P(B)$, depending on the prior distribution.

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.3.

Proposition 2. Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . Let

P be parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

Q be parametrized according to eqs. (4) with parameters $0 < a' < 1$ and $0 \leq p', q' \leq 1$.

Minimizing the IKL-divergence between Q and P with respect to a' and q' implies that

(i) $q' = q$ and $a' = a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot l)$ with $l = l_{IKL} = 1$.

(ii) Q is a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$.

$$(iii) \quad Q = \begin{cases} \neq P_0^* & \text{if } p' = 0 \\ = P & \text{if } p' = p \\ \neq P_1^* & \text{if } p' = 1 \end{cases}$$

where $P_0^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee \neg B)$ and $P_1^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee B)$.

(iv) $Q(A) = P(A)$ for all $p' \in [0, 1]$.

(v) $Q(B) = P(B) + (p' - p) \cdot Q(A)$ for all $p' \in [0, 1]$, i. e. $Q(B) = P(B)$ for $p' = p$ and $Q(B) > P(B)$ for $p' > p$ and $Q(B) < P(B)$ for $p' < p$.

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.4.

Let us state the following corollary, before we come to discussion.

Corollary 1. *Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . Let*

P be parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

Q be parametrized according to eqs. (4) with parameters $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$,

$p' = 1$,

$f : \mathbb{R}_0^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denote a strictly convex function with $f(0) = 1$, $f(0) := \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} f(x)$ and $f'(0) := \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} f'(x)$.

Iff f satisfies $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'(x) = 0$, then

$$Q = P_1^*$$

where $P_1^(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee B)$ and Q is obtained by minimizing F_f with respect to a' and q' .*

The proof of the corollary is given in section A.5.

Proposition 2 states that minimizing the IKL-divergence gives $Q \neq P_1^*$ if $p' = 1$. This is contrary to what Eva et al. (2020) claimed. They stated that minimizing (any) f -divergence yields $Q = P_1^*$ if $p' = 1$ (c.f. corollary 1 on p. 379). This is however not correct. If and only if $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'(x) = 0$, then $Q = P_1^*$ for $p' = 1$ (c.f. corollary 1). This condition is not fulfilled for the IKL-divergence, c.f. equation (8). Hence, minimizing the IKL-divergence is not consistent with Bayesian conditionalisation and that means that minimizing the IKL-divergence has lost part of its normative support.

Let us check that our conclusion about the IKL-divergence is correctly based: For $x > 0$, the IKL-divergence is $f_{IKL}(x) = -\log x$ and for $x = 0$ we have formally defined

$$f_{IKL}(0) := \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} f_{IKL}(x) = +\infty$$

and

$$f'_{IKL}(0) := \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} f'_{IKL}(x) = -\infty$$

but we haven't used $f_{IKL}(0)$ nor $f'_{IKL}(0)$ in the proof of proposition 2. We have used

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'_{IKL}(x) = -1$$

which is unproblematic. An other objection which could be forwarded is that the second term in (21) has to be omitted if $p' = 1$. This however is not reasonable as will be

shown next: If f is the IKL-divergence, i. e. $f = f_{IKL}$, then the limit $p' \rightarrow 1^-$ of the IKL-divergence between Q and P is

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{p' \rightarrow 1^-} F_{IKL} = & ap \lim_{p' \rightarrow 1^-} f_{IKL} \left(\frac{a' p'}{ap} \right) + a\bar{p} \lim_{p' \rightarrow 1^-} f_{IKL} \left(\frac{a' \bar{p}'}{a\bar{p}} \right) + \\ & \bar{a}q \lim_{p' \rightarrow 1^-} f_{IKL} \left(\frac{\bar{a}' q'}{\bar{a}q} \right) + \bar{a}\bar{q} \lim_{p' \rightarrow 1^-} f_{IKL} \left(\frac{\bar{a}' \bar{q}'}{\bar{a}\bar{q}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

If $0 < p' < 1$, then $q' = q$ and $a' = a$. Hence

$$\lim_{p' \rightarrow 1^-} F_{IKL} = ap \lim_{p' \rightarrow 1^-} f_{IKL} \left(\frac{p'}{p} \right) + a\bar{p} \lim_{p' \rightarrow 1^-} f_{IKL} \left(\frac{\bar{p}'}{\bar{p}} \right) + \bar{a}q f_{IKL}(1) + \bar{a}\bar{q} f_{IKL}(1)$$

This shows that if $p' \rightarrow 1^-$, then the first term converges to some constant, the second term converges to $+\infty$ and the third and fourth term are zero. Hence

$$\lim_{p' \rightarrow 1^-} F_{IKL} = ap f_{IKL} \left(\frac{1}{p} \right) + a\bar{p} \lim_{p' \rightarrow 1^-} f_{IKL} \left(\frac{\bar{p}'}{\bar{p}} \right).$$

Omitting the second term would remove the dominating term. Doing this however lacks reason. Similar reasoning applies to the case $p' \rightarrow 0^+$.

An other objection which could be forwarded against that $l_{IKL} = 1$ for $p' \in \{0, 1\}$ is that we could simply define $l_{IKL} = 1/p$ for $p' = 1$ and $l_{IKL} = 1/\bar{p}$ for $p' = 0$. This is however not correct since we nevertheless have

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'_{IKL}(x) = -1$$

and equation (25) formulates a necessary condition for a' to be a minimizer of F_f which imposes $a' = a$, i. e. $l = 1$.

The IKL-divergence has lost normative support but other divergences have gained normative support: Part (ii) of proposition 1 states that if the f -divergence satisfies the conditions from the proposition, then Q is a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$. In particular Q is continuous at $p' = 1$ and at $p' = 0$ and this is perfectly in line with our intuition.

4 Updating by Jeffrey conditionalisation

Consider $p' > p$. Proposition 1 states that $Q = P_1^*$ if $p' = 1$, i. e. that if condition (7) is satisfied, then minimizing the f -divergence between Q and P gives rise to the same a posteriori probability distribution as Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$. The result is limited to $p' = 1$ however. This poses the question whether minimizing f -divergences gives rise to probability distributions Q which are consistent with Jeffrey conditionalisation on

$\neg A \vee B$, i. e. whether $Q = Q_J$, where

$$Q_J(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee B) Q_J(\neg A \vee B) + P(\cdot | \neg(\neg A \vee B)) Q_J(\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \quad (14)$$

if $p < p' < 1$.

We discuss the latter in this section. Let's start with a lemma:

Lemma 3. *Let P , P_1^* and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . If*

P is parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

P_1^ is defined by Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$, i. e. $P_1^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee B)$,*

Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ (see eq. (14)), then

$$Q(A \wedge B) = P_1^*(A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \quad (15a)$$

$$Q(A \wedge \neg B) = Q(A \wedge \neg B) \quad (15b)$$

$$Q(\neg A \wedge B) = P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \quad (15c)$$

$$Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = P_1^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \quad (15d)$$

$$Q(A) = P_1^*(A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) + Q(A \wedge \neg B) \quad (15e)$$

$$Q(\neg A) = P_1^*(\neg A) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \quad (15f)$$

$$Q(B) = P_1^*(B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \quad (15g)$$

$$Q(\neg B) = Q(A \wedge \neg B) + P_1^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \quad (15h)$$

and if in addition $Q(A \wedge \neg B) > 0$, then

$$Q(A \wedge \neg B) > P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \quad (16a)$$

$$Q(A) > P_1^*(A) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \quad (16b)$$

$$Q(\neg B) > P_1^*(\neg B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B). \quad (16c)$$

The proof of the lemma is given in section A.6.

Next, we determine the parameters a' and q' as a function of p' .

Proposition 3. (Parameters Jeffrey conditionalisation) *Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . If*

P is parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ (see eq. (14)),

Q is parametrized according to eqs. (4) with parameters $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$, then

$$q' = q \quad \text{and} \quad a' = \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l} \quad (17)$$

where l is defined by $l := p'/p$.

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.7.

Proposition 3 holds for any $p' \in [0, 1]$. The suggestion is however not to update by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ if $p' < p$. If $p' < p$, the agent learns that $Q(\neg B|A) = 1 - p' > 1 - p = P(\neg B|A)$ or equivalently that $Q(\tilde{B}|A) = 1 - p' > 1 - p = P(\tilde{B}|A)$ where $\tilde{B} := \neg B$. If $Q(\tilde{B}|A) > P(\tilde{B}|A)$, the suggestion is to update by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \tilde{B} = \neg A \vee \neg B$, i. e. if $p' < p$, then the agent defines

$$Q(\cdot) := P(\cdot|\neg A \vee \neg B) Q(\neg A \vee \neg B) + P(\cdot|\neg(\neg A \vee \neg B)) Q(\neg(\neg A \vee \neg B)) \quad (18)$$

Consider the case $p' = 0$: If $p' = 0$, the reason to update by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ is that the update is then consistent with Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ and the reason to update by Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ and not on $\neg A \vee B$ if $p' = 0$ is the following: If $p' = 0$, then Bayesian conditionalisation respectively Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ yields $a' = 1$, c. f. eq. (17). If $a' = 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} Q(A \wedge B) &= a'p' = 0 & , & & Q(A \wedge \neg B) &= a'\bar{p}' = 1 \\ Q(\neg A \wedge B) &= \bar{a}'q' = 0 & , & & Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) &= \bar{a}'\bar{q}' = 0 \end{aligned}$$

This seems however unpalatable. An agent who learns that $P_0^*(B|A) = 0$, learns $P_0^*(A \wedge B) = 0$ and as a consequence by law of probability the probability mass $P(A \wedge B)$ has to be redistributed over $A \wedge \neg B$, $\neg A \wedge B$ and $\neg A \wedge \neg B$. The agent does not learn that $Q(A \wedge \neg B) = 1$ which would enforce $Q(A \wedge B) = 0$, $Q(\neg A \wedge B) = 0$ and $Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = 0$.

The next proposition determines the parameter a' (and q') if Q is determined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ (if $p' \geq p$) respectively by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ (if $p' \leq p$).

Proposition 4. (Parameters Jeffrey conditionalisation) Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . If

P is parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ if $p' \geq p$ (see eq. (14)) and by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ if $p' \leq p$ (see eq. (18)),

Q is parametrized according to eqs. (4) with parameters $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$, then

$$q' = q \quad \text{and} \quad a' = \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l_J}$$

where l_J is defined by

$$l_J := \begin{cases} p'/p & \text{if } p' \geq p \\ \bar{p}'/\bar{p} & \text{if } p' \leq p \end{cases}$$

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.8.

Having determined the parameters for Jeffrey conditionalisation and having determined the parameters which are obtained by minimizing f -divergences (see section 3), we can state the following consistency result:

Proposition 5. (Consistency) *Let P, P_0^*, P_1^*, Q_J and Q_f denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . If*

P is parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

P_0^ is defined by Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$, i. e. $P_0^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee \neg B)$,*

P_1^ is defined by Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$, i. e. $P_1^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee B)$,*

Q_J is defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ if $p' \geq p$ (see eq. (14)) and by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ if $p' \leq p$ (see eq. (18)),

Q_f is parametrized according to eqs (4) with parameters $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$ and defined by (a mechanism which gives) $q' = q$ and $a' := a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot l_f)$ where $l_f \geq 0$ (is mechanism specific), then

(i) $Q_J = P_0^$ if $p' = 0$, $Q_J = P$ if $p' = p$ and $Q_J = P_1^*$ if $p' = 1$.*

(ii) $Q_f = Q_J$ if $l_f = l_J$.

In particular, if Q_f is obtained by minimizing the KL-divergence, the Hellinger distance or the χ^2 -divergence, then $Q_f = Q_J$ only at $p' \in \{0, p, 1\}$ and if Q is obtained by minimizing the IKL-divergence, then $Q_f = Q_J$ only at $p' = p$.

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.9.

Figure 1 shows the differences $Q(A) - Q_J(A)$ respectively $Q(B) - Q_J(B)$ as a function of p' where Q denotes the update obtained by minimizing f -divergences and Q_J denotes the update obtained by Jeffrey conditionalisation. $Q(A)$ is consistent with $Q_J(A)$ at points where $Q(A) - Q_J(A) = 0$ and $Q(B)$ is consistent with $Q_J(B)$ at points where $Q(B) - Q_J(B) = 0$.

Proposition 5 states that the updates obtained from minimizing the IKL-divergence, the KL-divergence, the Hellinger distance and the χ^2 -divergence are (except a few points) not consistent with Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ respectively on $\neg A \vee \neg B$. It can be asked whether the afore mentioned updates are consistent with Jeffrey conditionalisation on some other propositional variable C ($C \neq \neg A \vee B$ respectively $C \neq \neg A \vee \neg B$). We do not have an answer to this question however we have formulated the problem in appendix B which if solved provides an answer.

Let us next include in our discussion an update strategy which has been proposed by Douven and Romeijn (2011) respectively Bradley (2005). They proposed to update by

Figure 1: Plot of $Q(A) - Q_J(A)$ and $Q(B) - Q_J(B)$. Q_J is obtained by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ (for $p' \geq p$) respectively on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ (for $p' \leq p$). Difference to f -divergences: to IKL-divergence (red), to KL-divergence (blue), to Hellinger distance (yellow), to χ^2 -divergence (green). $a = 0.8$, $p = 0.3$, $q = 0.7$.

(what they call) Adams conditioning. An agent who learns that the conditional probability $P(B|A)$ has changed from $P(B|A)$ to $Q(B|A)$, updates by Adams conditioning if she determines her a posteriori probability distribution Q by

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q(\cdot) = & P(\cdot|\neg A) P(\neg A) + P(\cdot|A \wedge B) Q(B|A) P(A) \\
 & + P(\cdot|A \wedge \neg B) Q(\neg B|A) P(A)
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

The following proposition determines the parameters a' , p' and q' in the case if an agent updates by Adams conditioning:

Proposition 6. (Parameters Adams conditioning) *Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . If*

P is parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

Q is defined by Adams conditioning (see eq. (19)),

Q is parametrized according to eqs. (4) with parameters $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$, then

$$q' = q \quad \text{and} \quad a' = \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l}$$

where $l = 1$.

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.10.

An immediate observation from the proposition is that the update obtained by Adams conditioning is identical to the update obtained by minimizing the IKL-divergence (c.f. proposition 2). Note, this is no new result. Douven and Romeijn (2011) already observed

this (c. f. Theorem 2, p. 652). However our proof is different from theirs. We characterised Adams conditioning by the parameters a' (l) and q' and then it is comparison with the parameters which are obtained by minimizing the IKL-divergence. Since the update formula given by equation (19) may still seem a bit mysterious, we have provided some further explanation in appendix C.

Let us return to the discussion of Jeffrey conditionalisation. An other question which arises concerns the revision of already revised credences. Consider an agent who learns 'If A , then B .'. The agent updates her a priori credences P and obtains a posteriori credences Q by some updating mechanism and by imposing $Q(B|A) = p' > p = P(B|A)$. Imagine the agent gets some new information about 'If A , then B .' and revises her credences Q by \tilde{P} which she obtains by the same updating mechanism and imposing $\tilde{P}(B|A) = P(B|A) = p < p' = Q(B|A)$, does this agent has a post-posteriori credences $\tilde{P} = P$? The following proposition gives an answer to this question.

Proposition 7. (*Revision of revised credences*) *Let P , \tilde{P} and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . Let*

P be parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

Q be parametrized according to eqs. (4) with parameters $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$

\tilde{P} be parametrized according to eqs. (4) with parameters $0 \leq a'', p'', q'' \leq 1$.

If $p' > p$, $p'' = p$ and Q is determined by some mechanism which gives $q' = q$ and $a' = a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot l)$ with some mechanism specific $l \geq 0$ and if \tilde{P} is determined by the same mechanism, i. e. $q'' = q'$ and $a'' = a'/(a' + \bar{a}' \cdot l')$, then

$$\tilde{P} = P$$

iff

$$l(p') \cdot l'(p) = 1.$$

In particular,

$$\begin{aligned} l_J(p') \cdot l'_J(p) &\neq 1, \\ l_{IKL}(p') \cdot l'_{IKL}(p) &= 1, & l_{KL}(p') \cdot l'_{KL}(p) &\neq 1 \\ l_H(p') \cdot l'_H(p) &\neq 1, & l_{\chi^2}(p') \cdot l'_{\chi^2}(p) &\neq 1 \end{aligned}$$

where the inequalities holds for least one $p' > p$ and the equality holds for all $p' > p$.

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.11.

The question which arises from the proposition is how should an agent who updates with Jeffrey conditionalisation or any of the f -divergences (KL, H, χ^2) proceed if she has to revise already revised credences? The proposition tells us that if the agent considers Q has her new a priori credences, then she will end up with a post-posteriori credences $\tilde{P} \neq P$

and the latter is implausible if $p'' = p$. An alternative approach could be to fix P as the a priori credences, i. e. to consider P in any revision stage as the a priori credences. In this case the agent would clearly obtain a post-posteriori credences $\tilde{P} = P$ if $p'' = p$. For any other p'' , i. e. $p'' \in [0, 1]$, $p'' \neq p$, this approach would equally give consistent revisions compared with prior revision stages. In case of IKL-updating, it is actually not clear, whether the agent steps from Q to \tilde{P} or from P to \tilde{P} since IKL-updating yields in both cases identical a post-posteriori credences.

Let us now step back to simple learning of 'If A , then B .': An other criteria to compare the updates is monotonicity. For Q obtained by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$, we obtain the following result:

Proposition 8. (Monotonicity) *Let P , P^* and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . If*

P is parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

P_1^ is defined by Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$, i. e. $P_1^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot | \neg A \vee B)$,*

Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ (see eq. (14)),

then

(i) $Q(A)$ and $Q(A \wedge \neg B)$ are strictly monotone decreasing functions of p' on $[0, 1]$. In particular:

$$\begin{array}{ll} Q(A) < P(A) & Q(A) > P_1^*(A) \\ Q(A \wedge \neg B) < P(A \wedge \neg B) & Q(A \wedge \neg B) > P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B) \end{array}$$

where the inequalities on the left-hand side hold for $p' \in (p, 1]$ and the inequalities on the right-hand side hold for $p' \in [p, 1)$.

(ii) $Q(B)$, $Q(A \wedge B)$, $Q(\neg A \wedge B)$ and $Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$ are strictly monotone increasing function of p' on $[0, 1]$. In particular:

$$\begin{array}{ll} Q(B) > P(B) & Q(B) < P_1^*(B) \\ Q(A \wedge B) > P(A \wedge B) & Q(A \wedge B) < P_1^*(A \wedge B) \\ Q(\neg A \wedge B) > P(\neg A \wedge B) & Q(\neg A \wedge B) < P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B) \\ Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) > P(\neg A \wedge \neg B) & Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) < P_1^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) \end{array}$$

where the inequalities on the left side hold for $p' \in (p, 1]$ and the inequalities on the right side hold for $p' \in [p, 1)$.

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.12.

Figure 2 and 3 show Q_J , Q_{IKL} , Q_{KL} , Q_H and Q_{χ^2} as functions of p' for $p' \in [0, 1]$ where Q_J is obtained by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ if $p' \geq p$ respectively by Jeffrey

Figure 2: Plot of $Q(A)$ and $Q(B)$ obtained by Jeffrey conditionalisation (black) on $\neg A \vee B$ (for $p' \geq p$) respectively on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ (for $p' \leq p$) and f -divergences: IKL-divergence (red), KL-divergence (blue), Hellinger distance (yellow), χ^2 -divergence (green). $a = 0.8$, $p = 0.3$, $q = 0.7$.

conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ if $p' \leq p$ and Q_{IKL} , Q_{KL} , Q_H and Q_{χ^2} are obtained by minimizing the IKL-divergence, the KL-divergence, the Hellinger distance and the χ^2 -divergence. The figures show that Q_J is monotone on $[p, 1]$ respectively on $[0, p]$. $Q_H(B)$ seems not to be monotone on $[p, 1]$ (see figure 2b) and $Q_{KL}(A \wedge B)$ and $Q_H(A \wedge B)$ are not monotone on $[p, 1]$ (see figure 3a). Q_{IKL} is in some cases constant (see figures 2a, 3c and 3d). Similar results on non-monotonicity have already been observed by Hartmann and Hahn (2021).

The last remark in this section concerns the interpretation of Jeffrey conditionalisation (on $\neg A \vee B$) as normalisation. See for this purpose figure 4. There are four squares $A \wedge B, \dots, \neg A \wedge \neg B$ and each square occurs with some probability $P(A \wedge B), \dots, P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$. Firstly, consider the case $p' = 1$, i. e. $P_1^*(B|A) = 1$. The latter is equivalent to $P_1^*(\neg A \vee B) = 1$ (c. f. section 2) respectively to $P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B) = 0$, i. e. the square (event) $A \wedge \neg B$ does not occur and hence one of the other three squares (events) must occur. The Bayesian update P_1^* is just normalisation of the three probabilities $P(A \wedge B)$, $P(\neg A \wedge B)$ and $P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$ with respect to the sum of the prior probabilities of $A \wedge B$, $\neg A \wedge B$ and $\neg A \wedge \neg B$, i. e. with respect to $P(\neg A \vee B)$ since $P(\neg A \vee B) = P(A \wedge B) + P(\neg A \wedge B) + P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$. Comparison with equations (1) and (2) show that this is indeed the case:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1^*(A \wedge B) &= \frac{P(A \wedge B)}{P(\neg A \vee B)} \\
 P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B) &= \frac{P(\neg A \wedge B)}{P(\neg A \vee B)} & P_1^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) &= \frac{P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)}{P(\neg A \vee B)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Next, consider the case $p' < 1$ and learning $Q(B|A) = p'$. In this case the a posteriori

Figure 3: Plot of Q obtained by Jeffrey conditionalisation (black) on $\neg A \vee B$ (for $p' \geq p$) respectively on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ (for $p' \leq p$) and f -divergences: IKL-divergence (red), KL-divergence (blue), Hellinger distance (yellow), χ^2 -divergence (green). $a = 0.8$, $p = 0.3$, $q = 0.7$.

probability of $A \wedge \neg B$ is not zero but $a'\bar{p}'$. Hence the sum of the posteriori probabilities of the other three events is $Q(\neg A \vee B)$, i. e. $1 - a'\bar{p}'$. The normalisation factor from conditionalising on the material conditional has to be normalized to obtain the normalisation factor for Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$, i. e.

$$\frac{P(\neg A \vee B)}{Q(\neg A \vee B)}$$

Hence we expect that

$$\begin{aligned} Q(A \wedge B) &= \frac{P(A \wedge B)}{P(\neg A \vee B)} \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) = P_1^*(A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \\ Q(\neg A \wedge B) &= \frac{P(\neg A \wedge B)}{P(\neg A \vee B)} \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) = P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \\ Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) &= \frac{P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)}{P(\neg A \vee B)} \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) = P_1^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \end{aligned}$$

and comparison with lemma 3 shows that this is indeed true.

	B	$\neg B$
A	$P(A \wedge B)$	$P(A \wedge \neg B)$
$\neg A$	$P(\neg A \wedge B)$	$P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$

Figure 4: The figure visualizes learning $P_1^*(B|A) = 1$ which is equivalent to learning $P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B) = 0$.

From last remark it is only a tiny step to the Judy Benjamin problem (van Fraassen, 1981, p. 377).

5 Judy Benjamin problem

A soldier, Judy Benjamin, is dropped with her platoon in a territory that is divided in two halves, Red Territory and Blue Territory, respectively, with each territory in turn being divided in equal parts, Second Company Area and Headquarters Company Area, thus forming four quadrants of roughly equal size. Because the platoon was dropped at more or less the centre of the whole territory, Judy Benjamin deems it equally likely that

they are in one quadrant as that they are in any of the others. They then receive the following radio message: ‘I can’t be sure where you are. If you are in Red Territory, then the odds are 3: 1 that you are in Second Company Area’. After this, the radio contact breaks down. Supposing that Judy accepts this message, how should she adjust her degrees of belief? (The formulation is from *Eva et al. (2020, p. 476)*.)

We define the following representation:

A : ‘Judy lands in Red Territory.’, $\neg A$: ‘Judy lands in Blue Territory.’

B : ‘Judy lands in Second Company Area.’, $\neg B$: ‘Judy lands in Headquarters Area.’

Note, given the parameterization (1) of P , the parameters are $a = 1/2$, $p = 1/2$ and $q = 1/2$. Figure 5 shows the probability distributions P , P_1^* , Q_{IKL} obtained by minimizing the IKL-divergence and Q_J obtained by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$.

If $p' = 1$, then Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ gives $P_1^*(A) = 1/3$. This matches perfectly with our intuition. In this case Judy learns that she is not in the quadrant $A \wedge \neg B$ but she has no idea in which of the other three quadrants she is. Hence all quadrants are equally likely for her, i. e. the probability of $P_1^*(A \wedge B) = P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B) = P_1^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = 1/3$ and $P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B) = 0$.

If $p' = 3/4 < 1$, then the probability of $A \wedge \neg B$ is not zero but $a'\bar{p}'$ and for Jeffrey conditionalisation the remaining probability mass is equally distributed over the other three quadrants. This gives $Q(A \wedge \neg B) = 0.1$ and $Q(A \wedge B) = Q(\neg A \wedge B) = Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = 0.3$. Minimizing the IKL-divergence attributes to $A \wedge B$ all probability mass which is subtracted from $A \wedge \neg B$ to keep $P(A) = Q(A)$ constant.

We are aware that there are people who have other intuitions like the one given by minimizing the IKL-divergence. We just want to point out that it is unintuitive to have P_1^* as intuition if $p' = 1$ and at the same time the intuition Q_{IKL} for $p' < 1$. If your intuition is Q_{IKL} for $p' < 1$, then you should define P_1^* accordingly by conditionalising on A and this gives $P_1^*(A \wedge B) = 0.5$, $P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B) = 0$, $P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B) = 0.25$ and $P_1^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = 0.25$.

The Judy Benjamin problem allows equally the interpretation of a game (respectively a bet). The game is to distribute money on the quadrants after learning $Q(B|A) = 3/4$. The probability distributions Q_J and Q_{IKL} both satisfy the condition $Q(B|A) = 3/4$. The question is then, do you think that Q_{IKL} is the better choice than Q_J or vice versa? If $p' = 1$, you learn that $P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B) = 0$, and if you consider Q_{IKL} , then you have to put half of your money on $A \wedge B$. Someone who did not have this learning experience and just is told that there are three squares, would certainly put a third of the money on each square.

Figure 5: The subfigures show the probability distributions P , Q by minimizing the IKL-divergence, Q by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ and P_1^* by Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ for the Judy Benjamin problem. For the subfigures b) and c) we have assumed $Q(B|A) = p' = 3/4$.

6 Lena the scientist problem

Lena is considering a set of mutually exclusive (but not logically exhaustive) scientific hypotheses H_1, \dots, H_n and their relationship to a possible future experimental outcome E . Conditional on any of the H_i 's, E has a low probability of being observed.

Case 1: Based on previous experience, Lena strongly believes that E will in fact be observed. In light of the fact that all of the considered theories conflict with this belief (since $P(E|H_i)$ is low for all i), she thinks that all of the considered theories are probably false, and a new theory is needed. However, one of her research assistants then informs her that the probability of E conditioned on H_1 was previously miscalculated, and is actually very high, that is, Lena learns the conditional 'If H_1 , then probably E '. Delighted to learn that one of her theories gives reasonable predictions of future experiments, Lena increases both the conditional probability of E given H_1 and the overall probability of H_1 .

Case 2: Based on previous experience, Lena strongly believes that E will not be observed. She is satisfied that all of the candidate theories cohere with this belief. However, one of her research assistants then informs her that the probability of E conditioned on H_1 was previously miscalculated, and is actually very high, that is, Lena learns the conditional 'If H_1 , then probably E '. As well as increasing the conditional probability of E given H_1 , Lena also dramatically reduces her belief in H_1 , since it now conflicts with her belief that

E won't be observed.

Case 3: Owing to a lack of relevant evidence, Lena is agnostic about whether E will be observed. One of her research assistants then informs her that the probability of E conditioned on H_1 was previously miscalculated, and is actually very high, that is, Lena learns the conditional 'If H_1 , then probably E '. Lena increases the conditional probability of E given H_1 , but keeps the probability of H_1 fixed, since she is indifferent about whether E will be observed, and so doesn't consider H_1 's evidential relationship to E to bear on its plausibility.

(The formulation is from Eva et al. (2020, p. 490).)

We consider the case $n = 1$. This does not limit generality since it can still be assumed that there are other hypothesis which are true under some conditions if $\neg H_1$ is true. Let us further slightly change the notation. We call A the hypothesis and we call B the evidence. We assign some numbers to the probabilities, since this allows us to observe more easily the updates. The story states that $P(B|A)$ is low. We set $P(B|A) = 0.1$. In case 1 we set $P(B) = 0.9$ since $P(B)$ is considered as big. In case 2 we set $P(B) = 0.1$ since $P(B)$ is considered as small and in case 3 we set $P(B) = 0.5$ since Lena is agnostic.

Figure 6 shows three probability distributions P which satisfy the respective conditions stated in the cases. The story further states that Lena learns 'If A , then B .' has high probability. We assume $Q(B|A) = 0.9$. Figure 7 shows Q obtained by Jeffrey condition-alisation on $\neg A \vee B$.

	B	$\neg B$		B	$\neg B$		B	$\neg B$
A	0.01	0.09	A	0.01	0.09	A	0.01	0.09
$\neg A$	0.89	0.01	$\neg A$	0.09	0.81	$\neg A$	0.49	0.41
	(a) $q = 0.89/0.9$			(b) $q = 0.09/0.9$			(c) $q = 0.49/0.9$	

Figure 6: The figures show the probability distributions P . In all three cases $a = 0.1$, $p = 0.1$.

Let us shortly compare our result with the intuition of Eva et al. (2020). In case 1 the intuition of Eva et al. (2020) is that $Q(A) > P(A)$. In contrast our result is that $Q(A) < P(A)$. Note, $Q(A) > P(A)$ would require that $Q(A \wedge B) + Q(A \wedge \neg B) > P(A)$. The term

$$Q(A \wedge \neg B) = a' \bar{p}' = \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l} \bar{p}'$$

	B	$\neg B$
A	0.011	0.001
$\neg A$	0.977	0.011

	B	$\neg B$
A	0.011	0.001
$\neg A$	0.099	0.889

	B	$\neg B$
A	0.011	0.001
$\neg A$	0.538	0.450

Figure 7: The figures show the probability distributions Q after learning $Q(B|A) = 0.9$ and updating by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$. The probability distributions P are given in figure 6. The quadrants which are within the green surrounded area gained probability mass whereas the quadrant with the dotted red cross lost probability mass.

decreases³ for Jeffrey conditionalisation and for IKL-minimization if p' increases and it vanishes if $p' = 1$. Having the intuition that $Q(A) > P(A)$ would require that the probability mass which is lost at $A \wedge \neg B$ is shifted to $A \wedge B$ and this would only give $Q(A) = P(A)$. Hence having the intuition that $Q(A) > P(A)$ would require in addition that probability mass would have to be shifted from $\neg A \wedge B$ and $\neg A \wedge \neg B$ to $A \wedge B$ in order that $Q(A) > P(A)$. Such big probability shift to $A \wedge B$ is however implausible. Plausible is instead that $Q(A \wedge B) > P(A \wedge B)$ and Jeffrey updating yields exactly this, c. f. figures 6, 7.

The reasoning for cases 2 and 3 goes the same way and is not repeated.

Eva et al. (2020, p. 492) proposed to update P by minimizing the IKL-divergence with respect to the following two constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{constraint 1: } & Q(B|A) = p' \\ \text{constraint 2: } & \begin{cases} Q(A) > P(A) & \text{if } P(B) > 1/2 \\ Q(A) = P(A) & \text{if } P(B) = 1/2 \\ Q(A) < P(A) & \text{if } P(B) < 1/2 \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

The updating strategy is supposed to determine the parameters $a' \in (0, 1)$ and $q' \in (0, 1)$. The second constraint is a constraint on a' . Determining q' is independent of a' , c. f. the proof of proposition 2. It gives in all three cases $q' = q$. The second constraint limits the domain where a' can be found. Since $Q(A) = a'$ and $P(A) = a$, the domains are as follows:

$$\begin{cases} (a, 1) & \text{if } P(B) > 1/2 \\ \{a\} & \text{if } P(B) = 1/2 \\ (0, a) & \text{if } P(B) < 1/2 \end{cases}$$

³ l is always positive. Hence $\frac{a}{a+\bar{a}l} < 1$.

The IKL divergence as a function of a' has one (and only one) minimum on the domain $(0, 1)$. The minimum is at $a' = a$. Thus the IKL divergence has no minimum on the domain $(0, a)$ respectively on the domain $(a, 1)$. This means that the updating strategy does not provide any update in the cases $P(B) > 1/2$ and $P(B) < 1/2$. If the agent accepts in these cases $a' = a \pm \epsilon$ with arbitrarily small $\epsilon > 0$, then the constraints $Q(A) > P(A)$ respectively $Q(A) < P(A)$ are theoretically satisfied but $a' \approx a$ respectively $Q(A) \approx P(A)$ and this is intuitively not $Q(A) > P(A)$ respectively $Q(A) < P(A)$.

7 Updating by Jeffrey conditionalisation

An agent who updates her probability distribution P by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ decreases the probability of $A \wedge \neg B$ and increases the probabilities of $A \wedge B$, $\neg A \wedge B$ and $\neg A \wedge \neg B$ (c.f. proposition 8). Next, we consider how updating changes the conditional probabilities $P(B|A)$, $P(\neg B|A)$, $P(B|\neg A)$, $P(\neg B|\neg A)$, $P(A|B)$, $P(\neg A|B)$, $P(A|\neg B)$, $P(\neg A|\neg B)$. We start with a lemma for Bayesian conditionalisation.

Lemma 4. *Let P and P_1^* denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . If*

P is parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

P_1^ is defined by Bayesian conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$, i. e. $P_1^*(\cdot) := P(\cdot|\neg A \vee B)$,*

then

- | | |
|--|---|
| (i) $P_1^*(B A) > P(B A)$ | (v) $P_1^*(\neg B \neg A) = P(\neg B \neg A)$ |
| (ii) $P_1^*(\neg B A) < P(\neg B A)$ | (vi) $P_1^*(B \neg A) = P(B \neg A)$ |
| (iii) $P_1^*(A \neg B) < P(A \neg B)$ | (vii) $P_1^*(\neg A B) = P(\neg A B)$ |
| (iv) $P_1^*(\neg A \neg B) > P(\neg A \neg B)$ | (viii) $P_1^*(A B) = P(A B)$ |

The proof of the lemma is given in section A.13.

Next, we show that we get a similar result if $p' < 1$ and Q is obtained by Jeffrey conditionalisation.

Proposition 9. (Conditional probabilities) *Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . If*

P is parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ (see eq. (14)),

$Q(B|A) =: p' > p$,

then

- | | |
|---|---|
| <p>(i) $Q(B A) > P(B A)$</p> <p>(ii) $Q(\neg B A) < P(\neg B A)$</p> <p>(iii) $Q(A \neg B) < P(A \neg B)$</p> <p>(iv) $Q(\neg A \neg B) > P(\neg A \neg B)$</p> | <p>(v) $Q(\neg B \neg A) = P(\neg B \neg A)$</p> <p>(vi) $Q(B \neg A) = P(B \neg A)$</p> <p>(vii) $Q(\neg A B) = P(\neg A B)$</p> <p>(viii) $Q(A B) = P(A B)$</p> |
|---|---|

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.14.

Let us compare the result of the proposition with the corresponding outcomes from minimizing f -divergences. We considered the a priori probability distribution defined in figure 9a and then obtained the values in tables 1 and 2. The conditional probabilities obtained from the Jeffrey conditionalisation confirm proposition 9. The conditional probabilities obtained from minimizing f -divergences show that updating by minimizing f -divergences does not keep the conditional probabilities $Q(A|B)$ and $Q(\neg A|B)$ constant and this is counter-intuitive. Learning $Q(B|A) = p' > p$ changes by definition $P(B|A)$ and by law of probability $P(\neg B|A)$ and we expect that $P(\neg A|\neg B)$ changes and by law of probability $P(A|\neg B)$. However we do not expect that $P(A|B)$ and $P(\neg A|B)$ change.

	B	$\neg B$		B	$\neg B$
A	0.4	0.3		0.48	0.16
$\neg A$	0.2	0.1		0.24	0.12
	(a) P			(b) Q	

Figure 8: The figures show the a priori probability distribution P and the a posteriori probability distribution Q obtained from Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ after learning $Q(B|A) = 3/4$. The data presented here is used as input data in figure 3 and tables 1 and 2.

Let us consider an other issue: Our intuition is that learning 'If A , then B .' and learning 'If $\neg B$, then $\neg A$.' should be equivalent, i. e. imposing a new value to $P(B|A)$ (i. e. $Q(B|A)$) should be equivalent to imposing a new value to $P(\neg A|\neg B)$ (i. e. $Q(\neg A|\neg B)$). Our intuition is that in both cases the agent should end up with the same a posteriori probability distribution Q . The next proposition states, that this is true if the agent updates by Jeffrey conditionalisation.

Proposition 10. (Equivalence result 1) *Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . Let*

Update	$Q(B A)$	$Q(\neg B A)$	$Q(\neg A \neg B)$	$Q(A \neg B)$
P	0.57	0.43	0.25	0.75
Jeffrey	0.75	0.25	0.43	0.57
IKL	0.75	0.25	0.36	0.64
KL	0.75	0.25	0.38	0.62
H	0.75	0.25	0.37	0.63
χ^2	0.75	0.25	0.39	0.61

Table 1: The table shows the conditional probabilities ($Q(B|A)$, $Q(\neg B|A)$, $Q(\neg A|\neg B)$ and $Q(A|\neg B)$) obtained by different updating strategies after learning that $Q(B|A) = 3/4$ and having the a priori probability distribution as shown in figure 9a. The second line from the top shows the a priori value of the conditional probabilities.

Update	$Q(B \neg A)$	$Q(\neg B \neg A)$	$Q(A B)$	$Q(\neg A B)$
P	0.67	0.33	0.67	0.33
Jeffrey	0.67	0.33	0.67	0.33
IKL	0.67	0.33	0.72	0.28
KL	0.67	0.33	0.71	0.29
H	0.67	0.33	0.70	0.30
χ^2	0.67	0.33	0.72	0.28

Table 2: The table shows the conditional probabilities ($Q(B|\neg A)$, $Q(\neg B|\neg A)$, $Q(A|B)$ and $Q(\neg A|B)$) obtained by different updating strategies after learning that $Q(B|A) = 3/4$ and having the a priori probability distribution as shown in figure 9a. The second line from the top shows the a priori value of the conditional probabilities.

P be parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

Q be defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ (see eq. (14)),

$Q(B|A) = p' > p$.

Let \tilde{P} and \tilde{Q} denote the probability distributions which are defined over the propositional variables $\tilde{A} := \neg B$ and $\tilde{B} := \neg A$. Let

\tilde{P} be defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{P}(\tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) &:= P(\neg A \wedge \neg B) & , & & \tilde{P}(\tilde{A} \wedge \neg \tilde{B}) &:= P(A \wedge \neg B) \\ \tilde{P}(\neg \tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) &:= P(\neg A \wedge B) & , & & \tilde{P}(\neg \tilde{A} \wedge \neg \tilde{B}) &:= P(A \wedge B) \end{aligned}$$

\tilde{Q} be defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg \tilde{A} \vee \tilde{B}$ (c.f. equation (14)).

If $\tilde{Q}(\tilde{B}|\tilde{A}) = Q(\neg A|\neg B)$, then

$$Q = \tilde{Q}^T$$

where \tilde{Q}^T is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{Q}^T(A \wedge B) &:= \tilde{Q}(\neg A \wedge \neg B) & , & & \tilde{Q}^T(A \wedge \neg B) &:= \tilde{Q}(A \wedge \neg B) \\ \tilde{Q}^T(\neg A \wedge B) &:= \tilde{Q}(\neg A \wedge B) & , & & \tilde{Q}^T(\neg A \wedge \neg B) &:= \tilde{Q}(A \wedge B) \end{aligned}$$

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.15.

Let us compare the result of the proposition with the corresponding outcomes from minimizing f -divergences. We considered the a priori probability distribution defined in figure 9a and then obtained the values in table 3. The values obtained for Jeffrey conditionalisation confirm proposition 10. The a posteriori probability distribution obtained from minimizing f -divergences (IKL, KL, Hellinger and χ^2) show that learning 'If A , then B .' and imposing a new value to $P(B|A)$ (i. e. $Q(B|A)$) is not equivalent to learning 'If $\neg B$, then $\neg A$.' and imposing a new value to $P(\neg A|\neg B)$ (i. e. $Q(\neg A|\neg B)$).

Update	Learning	$Q(A \wedge B)$	$Q(A \wedge \neg B)$	$Q(\neg A \wedge B)$	$Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$
Jeffrey	$Q(B A) = 3/4$	0.48	0.16	0.24	0.12
	$Q(\neg A \neg B) = 3/7$	0.48	0.16	0.24	0.12
IKL	$Q(B A) = 3/4$	0.525	0.175	0.2	0.1
	$Q(\neg A \neg B) \approx 0.36$	0.4	0.255	0.2	0.145
KL	$Q(B A) = 3/4$	0.514	0.171	0.210	0.105
	$Q(\neg A \neg B) \approx 0.38$	0.407	0.242	0.203	0.148
H	$Q(B A) = 3/4$	0.519	0.173	0.205	0.103
	$Q(\neg A \neg B) \approx 0.37$	0.412	0.240	0.206	0.142
χ^2	$Q(B A) = 3/4$	0.505	0.168	0.218	0.109
	$Q(\neg A \neg B) \approx 0.39$	0.416	0.228	0.208	0.147

Table 3: The table shows the values for Q obtained from different updating strategies and different learned conditional probabilities. The a priori probability distribution P is defined in figure 9a. The values for $Q(\neg A|\neg B)$ are obtained as follows: for IKL for instance the value is $Q(\neg A|\neg B) = Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B)/Q(\neg B) = 0.1/(0.175 + 0.1) \approx 0.36$.

Let consider an other slightly different issue: Our intuition is that learning 'If A , then B .' and imposing a new value to $P(B|A)$ (i. e. $Q(B|A)$) and learning 'If A , then B .' and imposing a new value to $P(A \wedge B)$ (i. e. $Q(A \wedge B)$) should be equivalent. Our intuition is that in both cases the agent should end up with the same a posteriori probability distribution Q . The next proposition states, that this is true if the agent updates by Jeffrey conditionalisation.

Proposition 11. (Equivalence result 2) *Let P , Q and Q_1, \dots, Q_8 denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . Let*

P be parametrized according to eqs. (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$,

Q be defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ (see eq. (14)),

$Q(B|A) = p' > p$.

If Q_1, \dots, Q_8 are defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ (c. f. equation (14)) and

$$Q_1(A \wedge B) = Q(A \wedge B) \quad (20a)$$

$$Q_2(A \wedge \neg B) = Q(A \wedge \neg B) \quad (20b)$$

$$Q_3(\neg A \wedge B) = Q(\neg A \wedge B) \quad (20c)$$

$$Q_4(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) \quad (20d)$$

$$Q_5(B|A) = Q(B|A) \quad (20e)$$

$$Q_6(\neg B|A) = Q(\neg B|A) \quad (20f)$$

$$Q_7(\neg A|\neg B) = Q(\neg A|\neg B) \quad (20g)$$

$$Q_8(A|\neg B) = Q(A|\neg B) \quad (20h)$$

then

$$Q_1 = Q_2 = Q_3 = Q_4 = Q_5 = Q_6 = Q_7 = Q_8 = Q.$$

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.16.

The proof boils down to simple parameter identification. The probability distribution Q is determined by three parameters (a' , p' and q'). Jeffrey conditionalisation determines $q' = q$ and $a' = a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot l_J)$, where $l_J = p'/p$ (for $p' > p$). Hence there remains only one undetermined parameter (p') and imposing some value to the probability of the conjunctions respectively conditional probabilities (equations (20)) removes this undetermination. The minimization of f -divergences determines equally $q' = q$ and $a' = a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot l)$ where l is some function of p' . Hence there remains equally only one undetermined parameter (p') and an agent may impose some value to the probability of the conjunctions or conditional probabilities and remove this underdetermination. The only restriction is that the condition must determine p' uniquely and this depends on l .

An agent who learns 'If A , then B .' and updates by Jeffrey conditionalisation may impose to any of the probabilities⁴ $P(A \wedge B)$, $P(A \wedge \neg B)$, $P(\neg A \wedge B)$ and $P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$ and to any of the conditional probabilities $P(B|A)$, $P(\neg B|A)$, $P(\neg A|\neg B)$ and $P(A|\neg B)$ a new value and she will end up with the same a posteriori probability distribution Q if the new value which is imposed is given by Q . The agent however can not impose to the conditional probabilities $P(\neg B|\neg A)$, $P(B|\neg A)$, $P(\neg A|B)$ and $P(A|B)$ a new value since they remain constant respectively are independent of p' and a' (c. f. proposition 9).

Note, proposition 10 makes a statement about how learning 'If A , then B .' and learning 'If $\neg B$, then $\neg A$.' compare whereas proposition 11 just considers learning 'If A , then

⁴This includes unions, e. g. the agent may equally impose to $P(A) = P(A \wedge B) + P(A \wedge \neg B)$ a new value.

B .'. An agent who learns 'If A , then B .' and updates by Jeffrey conditionalisation conditionalises on $\neg A \vee B$ and an agent who learns 'If $\neg B$, then $\neg A$.' conditionalises on $\neg(\neg B) \vee \neg A = \neg A \vee B$, i. e. they both conditionalise on the same propositional variable. Hence, the difference between learning 'If A , then B .' and learning 'If $\neg B$, then $\neg A$.' lies somewhere else: An agent who learns 'If A , then B .' has a priori credences P and an agent who learns 'If $\neg B$, then $\neg A$.' has a priori credences \tilde{P} (c.f. proposition 10) and although \tilde{P} is defined by means of P , the parameters are (in general) different $a \neq \tilde{a}$, $p \neq \tilde{p}$ and $q \neq \tilde{q}$, see figure 9. Proposition 10 tells us that Jeffrey conditionalisation gives nevertheless rise to an a posteriori probability distributions Q and \tilde{Q} which are identical after backward transformation⁵ of \tilde{Q} . In contrast, the minimization of f -divergences does not give rise to a posteriori probability distributions Q and \tilde{Q} which are identical after backward transformation (c.f. table 3).

	B	$\neg B$
A	0.4	0.3
$\neg A$	0.2	0.1

(a) P

	\tilde{B}	$\neg\tilde{B}$
\tilde{A}	0.1	0.3
$\neg\tilde{A}$	0.2	0.4

(b) \tilde{P}

Figure 9: The figures show the a priori probability distributions P and \tilde{P} . A and B are propositional variables. $\tilde{A} := \neg B$ and $\tilde{B} := \neg A$. An agent who learns 'If A , then B .' considers P ($a = 0.7$, $p = 4/7$, $q = 2/3$) as her a priori probability distribution. If the agent however learns 'If \tilde{A} , then \tilde{B} .' then she considers \tilde{P} ($\tilde{a} = 0.4$, $\tilde{p} = 1/4$, $\tilde{q} = 1/3$) as her a priori probability distribution.

In practise, if the agent is a person⁶ and learns 'If A , then B .' she will probably not do this two-step process: first impose to any of the probabilities of the conjunctions $P(A \wedge B)$, $P(A \wedge \neg B)$, $P(\neg A \wedge B)$ and $P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$ or to any of the conditional probabilities $P(B|A)$, $P(\neg B|A)$, $P(\neg A|\neg B)$, $P(A|\neg B)$ a new value and than (second) to update by Jeffrey conditionalisation. The agent will probably simply impose to some or all of probabilities of the conjunctions and conditional probabilities new values. The question is whether she does this in a consistent way, i. e. whether she does this such that $Q_1 = Q_2 = Q_3 = Q_4 = Q_5 = Q_6 = Q_7 = Q_8$ and whether she alters any of the conditional probabilities which should stay constant.

⁵The transformation given in proposition 10 which defines \tilde{Q}^T .

⁶In practise, the agent can be a computer/machine or a person. If the agent is a computer (program), then the program must get some specific input value for a specific probability - either for one of the probabilities of the conjunctions or for one of the conditional probabilities - and than the program can compute the update.

What concerns the representation of conditionals, this seems in view of proposition 11 not the foremost question. An agent does not have to answer the question whether $P(B|A)$ or $P(A \wedge B)$ better represents the conditional 'If A , then B '. An agent has to assign a new values to both $P(B|A)$ and $P(A \wedge B)$. If the agent actually updates by (Jeffrey) conditionalisation, then the foremost question seems which of these quantities can be best estimated by the agent.

8 Conclusion

We have shown in this article that simply conditionalising on the material conditional is a good and to our knowledge best answer to learning (non-) strict (indicative) conditionals. If the conditional is strict, the agent imposes $P_1^*(B|A) = 1$ (respectively $P_0^*(B|A) = 0$). The latter is equivalent to $\neg A \vee B$ (respectively $\neg A \vee \neg B$) and hence the agent conditionalises on $\neg A \vee B$ (respectively on $\neg A \vee \neg B$) (see section 2). If the conditional is non-strict, the agent imposes $Q(B|A) = p' < 1$. It has been an open question so far to which propositional variable an agent should conditionalise on in this case respectively whether there is such a propositional variable at all. We have shown that the agent should, in particular if the conditional is non-strict, conditionalise on $\neg A \vee B$ if $p < p' \leq 1$ respectively conditionalise on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ if $0 \leq p' < p$. This has the nice consequence that non-strict conditional and strict conditionals do not need to be distinguished by the theory. Furthermore, the propositional variable $\neg A \vee B$ (respectively $\neg A \vee \neg B$) states not only a truth condition for strict conditional, it states equally a truth condition if the conditional is non-strict. The probability of $\neg A \vee B$ (respectively of $\neg A \vee \neg B$) is however not the conditional probability $p' = Q(B|A)$ (respectively $1 - p' = Q(\neg B|A)$) but the probability $Q(\neg A \vee B) = 1 - a'p'$ (respectively $Q(\neg A \vee \neg B) = 1 - a'p'$).

Let us finish this article by shortly summarising our results: If Q is determined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$, then Q is continuous, monotone and by definition consistent with Jeffrey conditionalisation, i. e. Bayesian norms (c. f. section 4). Furthermore, the updates obtained for the Judy Benjamin problem and for Lena the scientist are consistent with our intuitions (c. f. sections 5 and 6). In section 7 we have shown that only the conditional probabilities $P(B|A)$, $P(\neg B|A)$, $P(\neg A|\neg B)$ and $P(A|\neg B)$ change by Jeffrey conditionalisation and this is consistent with our intuition since an agent who learns 'If A , then B .' has no learning about 'If $\neg A$, then B .' respectively 'If $\neg B$, then A .' Furthermore, we have shown that learning 'If A , then B .' is equivalent to learning 'If $\neg B$, then $\neg A$.' in case of Jeffrey conditionalisation. Lastly, we have shown that an agent is not forced to impose on $P(B|A)$ a new value and do the update. She can equally impose to any of the other probabilities which change a new value without changing the update.

A Proofs

A.1 Proof of lemma 1

Let $q' = q$, $p' = p$ and $l = 1$. Since $a' = a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot 1) = a$, $p' = p$ and $q' = q$, it follows that $Q = P$.

Let $q' = q$, $p' = 0$ and $l = 1/\bar{p}$. Then $a' = a/(a + \bar{a}/\bar{p}) = a\bar{p}/(a\bar{p} + \bar{a})$. In view of equations (3), it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} Q(A \wedge B) &= a'p' = 0 = P_0^*(A \wedge B) \\ Q(A \wedge \neg B) &= a'\bar{p}' = a' = a\bar{p}/(a\bar{p} + \bar{a}) = P_0^*(A \wedge \neg B) \\ Q(\neg A \wedge B) &= \bar{a}'q' = (1 - a') \cdot q = \bar{a}/(a\bar{p} + \bar{a}) \cdot q = P_0^*(\neg A \wedge B) \\ Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) &= \bar{a}'\bar{q}' = \bar{a}/(a\bar{p} + \bar{a}) \cdot \bar{q} = P_0^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) \end{aligned}$$

i. e. $Q = P_0^*$.

Let $q' = q$, $p' = 1$ and $l = 1/p$. Then $a' = a/(a + \bar{a}/p) = ap/(ap + \bar{a})$.

$$\begin{aligned} Q(A, B) &= a'p' = a' = \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}} = P_1^*(A, B) \\ Q(A, \neg B) &= a'\bar{p}' = 0 = P_1^*(A, \neg B) \\ Q(\neg A, B) &= \bar{a}'q' = (1 - a')q' = \left(1 - \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}}\right)q = \frac{\bar{a}}{ap + \bar{a}}q \\ &= \frac{\bar{a}q}{ap + \bar{a}} = P_1^*(\neg A, B) \\ Q(\neg A, \neg B) &= \bar{a}'\bar{q}' = (1 - a')(1 - q') = \frac{\bar{a}\bar{q}}{ap + \bar{a}} = P_1^*(\neg A, \neg B) \end{aligned}$$

i. e. $Q = P_1^*$

A.2 Proof of lemma 2

Clearly, iff $l : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$ is a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$, then $a' = a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot l)$ is a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$. Iff a' is a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$, then $Q(A \wedge B) = a'p'$, $Q(A \wedge \neg B) = a'\bar{p}'$, $Q(\neg A \wedge B) = \bar{a}'q$ and $Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = \bar{a}'\bar{q}'$ are continuous functions of p' on $[0, 1]$.

A.3 Proof of proposition 1

The proof is in part from Eva et al. (2020, p. 500) and extended where necessary.

Proof of (i): Let $p' \in [0, 1]$. The f -divergence between Q and P is

$$F_f = apf\left(\frac{a'p'}{ap}\right) + a\bar{p}f\left(\frac{a'\bar{p}'}{a\bar{p}}\right) + \bar{a}qf\left(\frac{\bar{a}'q'}{\bar{a}q}\right) + \bar{a}\bar{q}f\left(\frac{\bar{a}'\bar{q}'}{\bar{a}\bar{q}}\right). \quad (21)$$

Differentiating by q' respectively a' and setting the expressions equal to zero yields

$$0 = \bar{a}'f'\left(\frac{\bar{a}'q'}{\bar{a}q}\right) - \bar{a}'f'\left(\frac{\bar{a}'\bar{q}'}{\bar{a}\bar{q}}\right) \quad (22)$$

$$0 = p'f'\left(\frac{a'p'}{ap}\right) + \bar{p}'f'\left(\frac{a'\bar{p}'}{a\bar{p}}\right) - q'f'\left(\frac{\bar{a}'q'}{\bar{a}q}\right) - \bar{q}'f'\left(\frac{\bar{a}'\bar{q}'}{\bar{a}\bar{q}}\right) \quad (23)$$

Since $\bar{a}' > 0$ and f strictly convex, eq. (22) implies that $q' = q$. This reduces eq. (23) to

$$p'f'\left(\frac{a'p'}{ap}\right) + \bar{p}'f'\left(\frac{a'\bar{p}'}{a\bar{p}}\right) = f'\left(\frac{a'}{a}\right) \quad (24)$$

For any $a' \in (0, 1)$ there is a $l \in \mathbb{R}^+$ such that

$$l \cdot \frac{a'}{a} = \frac{\bar{a}'}{\bar{a}}.$$

Hence, we obtain for eq. (24)

$$p'f'\left(\frac{a'p'}{ap}\right) + \bar{p}'f'\left(\frac{a'\bar{p}'}{a\bar{p}}\right) = f'\left(\frac{a'}{a} \cdot l\right). \quad (25)$$

Note, if $f'(0) \in \mathbb{R}$, i.e. $f'(0) \neq \pm\infty$, then we can consider eq. (25) for $p' = 1$ and $p' = 0$ without concern. If $f'(0) = +\infty$ or $f'(0) = -\infty$, then the condition $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} xf'(x) = 0$ guarantees that the terms $p'f'\left(\frac{a'p'}{ap}\right) \in \mathbb{R}$ if $p' = 0$ respectively that $\bar{p}'f'\left(\frac{a'\bar{p}'}{a\bar{p}}\right) \in \mathbb{R}$ if $p' = 1$.

Let $p' = p$. Equation (25) reduces to

$$f'\left(\frac{a'}{a}\right) = f'\left(\frac{a'}{a} \cdot l\right).$$

Since f is convex, we obtain $l = 1$.

Next, let $p' = 1$: The second term in eq. (25) is zero. Hence, eq. (25) reduces to

$$f'\left(\frac{a'}{ap}\right) = f'\left(\frac{a'}{a} \cdot l\right)$$

and the convexity of f implies that $l = 1/p$.

Similarly, if $p' = 0$, then the first term in eq. (25) is zero. Hence, eq. (25) reduces to

$$f' \left(\frac{a'}{a\bar{p}} \right) = f' \left(\frac{a'}{a} \cdot l \right)$$

and the convexity of f implies that $l = 1/\bar{p}$.

It was shown by Eva et al. (2020, p. 500) that the likelihood ratios (13) satisfy (25) for $p' \in (p, 1)$. This clearly holds as well for $p' \in (0, p)$. Furthermore $l_{KL}(0) = l_H(0) = l_{\chi^2}(0) = 1/\bar{p}$, $l_{KL}(p) = l_H(p) = l_{\chi^2}(p) = 1$ and $l_{KL}(1) = l_H(1) = l_{\chi^2}(1) = 1/p$ (see eqs. (9), (10) and (11)).

Proof of (ii): Suppose $l = l(p')$ is not continuous at some point $\tilde{p}' \in [0, 1]$, i. e. $\lim_{p' \rightarrow \tilde{p}'} l(p') \neq l(\tilde{p}')$. Since f is strictly convex and in particular f' continuous, we obtain for the right-hand side of equation (25)

$$\lim_{p' \rightarrow \tilde{p}'} f' \left(\frac{a'}{a} \cdot l(p') \right) = f' \left(\frac{a'}{a} \cdot \lim_{p' \rightarrow \tilde{p}'} l(p') \right) \neq f' \left(\frac{a'}{a} \cdot l(\tilde{p}') \right).$$

and for the left-hand side of equation (25)

$$\lim_{p \rightarrow \bar{p}} \left[p' f' \left(\frac{a' p'}{ap} \right) + \bar{p}' f' \left(\frac{a' \bar{p}'}{a\bar{p}} \right) \right] = \tilde{p}' f' \left(\frac{a' \tilde{p}'}{ap} \right) + \bar{\tilde{p}}' f' \left(\frac{a' \tilde{p}'}{a\bar{p}} \right).$$

This contradicts equation (25). Therefore l must be a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$.

From lemma 2 it follows that Q is a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$.

Proof of (iii): The proof of (i) showed that $l = 1/\bar{p}$ if $p' = 0$, $l = 1$ if $p' = p$ and $l = 1/p$ if $p' = 1$. From lemma 1 it follows that $Q = P_0^*$ if $p' = 0$, $Q = P$ if $p' = p$ and $Q = P_1^*$ if $p' = 1$.

Proof of (iv): For $p' \in (p, 1)$ the proof is given in Eva et al. (2020, p. 500 f.). For $p' = 1$ respectively $p' \in [0, p]$, the proof does not require any modification.

A.4 Proof of proposition 2

The proof is in part from Eva et al. (2020, p. 500) respectively from the proof of proposition 1 and extended where necessary.

Proof of (i): Let $f = f_{IKL}$. Differentiating F_f (see eq. (21)) by q' respectively a' and setting the expressions equal to zero yields eqs. (22) and (23).

For any $p' \in [0, 1]$, since $\bar{a}' > 0$ and f_{IKL} strictly convex, eq. (22) implies that $q' = q$.

Let $l_{IKL} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ such that $l_{IKL} \cdot a'/a = \bar{a}'/\bar{a}$. This gives (c. f. proof of proposition 1)

$$p' f'_{IKL} \left(\frac{a' p'}{ap} \right) + \bar{p}' f'_{IKL} \left(\frac{a' \bar{p}'}{a \bar{p}} \right) = f'_{IKL} \left(\frac{a'}{a} \cdot l_{IKL} \right). \quad (26)$$

Note, $f'_{IKL}(0) = -\infty$ however $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'_{IKL}(x) = -1$. The latter guarantees that the terms $p' f'_{IKL} \left(\frac{a' p'}{ap} \right) \in \mathbb{R}$ if $p' = 0$ respectively that $\bar{p}' f'_{IKL} \left(\frac{a' \bar{p}'}{a \bar{p}} \right) \in \mathbb{R}$ if $p' = 1$.

If $p' = 0$, then $l_{IKL} = 1$ (see proof of proposition 1).

If $p' = 1$, then eq. (26) yields (since $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'_{IKL}(x) = -1$)

$$\frac{ap}{a'} + \frac{a\bar{p}}{a'} = \frac{a}{a' \cdot l_{IKL}} \quad (27)$$

or equivalently

$$\frac{a}{a'} = \frac{a}{a' \cdot l_{IKL}}$$

i. e. $l_{IKL} = 1$.

If $p' = 0$ we obtain again (27) and hence $l_{IKL} = 1$.

Eva et al. (2020, p. 500) showed that $l_{IKL} = 1$ for $p' \in (p, 1)$. The proof holds equally for $p' \in (0, p)$.

Proof of (ii): $l \equiv 1$ for $p' \in [0, 1]$. From lemma 2 follows that Q is a continuous function of p' on $[0, 1]$.

Proof of (iii): $l \equiv 1$ for $p' \in [0, 1]$. Hence $Q(A) = a' = a = P(A)$ for all $p' \in [0, 1]$.

Proof of (iv): For $p' \in (p, 1)$ the proof of (iv) is given in Eva et al. (2020, p. 500 f.). For $p' = 1$ respectively $p' \in [0, p]$, the proof does not require any modification. Since $l \equiv 1$ for $p' \in [0, 1]$, we obtain $Q(B) = P(B) + (p' - p) \cdot Q(A)$ for $p' \in [0, 1]$ and therefore $Q(B) = P(B)$ for $p' = p$, $Q(B) > P(B)$ for $p' > p$ and $Q(B) < P(B)$ for $p' < p$.

A.5 Proof of corollary 1

Proposition 1 (iii) states that if f satisfies $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'(x) = 0$ and $p' = 1$, then $Q = P_1^*$.

It remains to prove that $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'(x) = 0$ if $Q = P_1^*$ and $p' = 1$.

Q is parametrized by a' , p' and q' . $Q = P_1^*$ iff $q' = q$, $p' = 1$ and $a' = a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot l)$ where $l = 1/p$.

Minimizing F_f with respect to q' yields $q' = q$ (c. f. proof of proposition 1).

Differentiating F_f with respect to a' and setting the expression equal to zero yields (c. f. proof of proposition 1)

$$p' f' \left(\frac{a' p'}{ap} \right) + \bar{p}' f' \left(\frac{a' \bar{p}'}{a\bar{p}} \right) = f' \left(\frac{a'}{a} \cdot l \right). \quad (28)$$

with $l \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$.

If $p' = 1$ and $l = 1/p$, then

$$p' f' \left(\frac{a' p'}{ap} \right) = f' \left(\frac{a'}{a} \cdot l \right).$$

and hence

$$\lim_{p' \rightarrow 1^-} \bar{p}' f' \left(\frac{a' \bar{p}'}{a\bar{p}} \right) = 0$$

The latter is equivalent to $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} x f'(x) = 0$.

A.6 Proof of lemma 3

$$\begin{aligned} Q(A \wedge B) &= \frac{P((A \wedge B) \wedge (\neg A \vee B))}{P(\neg A \vee B)} Q(\neg A \vee B) \\ &\quad + \frac{P((A \wedge B) \wedge (A \wedge \neg B))}{P(\neg(\neg A \vee B))} Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \\ &= \frac{P(A \wedge B)}{P(\neg A \vee B)} Q(\neg A \vee B) + 0 \\ &= P_1^*(A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Q(A \wedge \neg B) &= \frac{P((A \wedge \neg B) \wedge (\neg A \vee B))}{P(\neg A \vee B)} Q(\neg A \vee B) \\ &\quad + \frac{P((A \wedge \neg B) \wedge (A \wedge \neg B))}{P(\neg(\neg A \vee B))} Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \\ &= 0 + 1 \cdot Q(A \wedge \neg B) = Q(A \wedge \neg B) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\neg A \wedge B) &= \frac{P((\neg A \wedge B) \wedge (\neg A \vee B))}{P(\neg A \vee B)} Q(\neg A \vee B) \\ &\quad + \frac{P((\neg A \wedge B) \wedge (A \wedge \neg B))}{P(\neg(\neg A \vee B))} Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \\ &= \frac{P(\neg A \wedge B)}{P(\neg A \vee B)} Q(\neg A \vee B) + 0 \\ &= P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) &= \frac{P((\neg A \wedge \neg B) \wedge (\neg A \vee B))}{P(\neg A \vee B)} Q(\neg A \vee B) \\
&\quad + \frac{P((\neg A \wedge \neg B) \wedge (A \wedge \neg B))}{P(\neg(\neg A \vee B))} Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \\
&= \frac{P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)}{P(\neg A \vee B)} Q(\neg A \vee B) + 0 \\
&= P_1^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B)
\end{aligned}$$

The proof of equations (15e)-(15h) follows from equations (15a)-(15d) and the proof of equation (16a)-(16c) is as follows:

$$Q(A \wedge \neg B) > 0 = P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B) = P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(A) &= Q(A \wedge B) + Q(A \wedge \neg B) \\
&= P_1^*(A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) + Q(A \wedge \neg B) \\
&= P_1^*(A) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) + Q(A \wedge \neg B) \\
&> P_1^*(A) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(\neg B) &= Q(A \wedge \neg B) + Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) \\
&= Q(A \wedge \neg B) + P_1^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \\
&= Q(A \wedge \neg B) + P_1^*(\neg B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \\
&> P_1^*(\neg B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B)
\end{aligned}$$

A.7 Proof of proposition 3

Let P_1^* denote the probability distribution over the propositional variables A and B which is defined by equations (2). From lemma 3 it follows that

$$Q(A \wedge B) = P_1^*(A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) = \frac{ap}{\bar{a} + ap} \cdot (1 - a'\bar{p}')$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(A) &= Q(A \wedge B) + Q(A \wedge \neg B) \\
&= \frac{ap}{\bar{a} + ap} \cdot (1 - a'\bar{p}') + a'\bar{p}' \\
&= \frac{ap - apa'\bar{p}' + \bar{a}a'\bar{p}' + apa'\bar{p}'}{\bar{a} + ap} \\
&= \frac{ap + \bar{a}a'\bar{p}'}{\bar{a} + ap}.
\end{aligned}$$

This gives

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(B|A) = p' &= \frac{Q(A \wedge B)}{Q(A)} \\
&= \frac{ap(1 - a'\bar{p}')}{ap + \bar{a}a'\bar{p}'}
\end{aligned}$$

or equivalently

$$p'(ap + \bar{a}a'\bar{p}') = ap(1 - a'\bar{p}')$$

or equivalently

$$\begin{aligned}
a'(\bar{a}p'\bar{p}' + app') &= ap - app' \\
&= ap(1 - p') \\
&= app'
\end{aligned}$$

i. e.

$$a' = \frac{app'}{(\bar{a}p' + ap)\bar{p}'} = \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'} = \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l}$$

where $l := p'/p$.

From lemma 3 it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
q' = Q(B|\neg A) &= \frac{Q(\neg A \wedge B)}{Q(\neg A)} \\
&= \frac{P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B)}{P_1^*(\neg A) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B)} \\
&= \frac{P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B)}{P_1^*(\neg A)} \\
&= \frac{\bar{a}q}{\bar{a}q + \bar{a}\bar{q}} = \frac{q}{q + \bar{q}} = q.
\end{aligned}$$

A.8 Proof of proposition 4

According to proposition 3, Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ determines a' as follows:

$$a' = \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'} = \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l}$$

where $l = p'/p$.

It can be verified (the proof is similar to the proof of proposition 3) that Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ determines a' as follows:

$$a' = \frac{a\bar{p}}{a\bar{p} + \bar{a}\bar{p}'} = \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l}$$

where $l = \bar{p}'/\bar{p}$.

Hence, if Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ (if $p' \geq p$) and by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee \neg B$ (if $p' \leq p$), then $q' = q$ and

$$a' = \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l_J}$$

where

$$l_J := \begin{cases} p'/p & \text{if } p' \geq p \\ \bar{p}'/\bar{p} & \text{if } p' \leq p \end{cases}$$

A.9 Proof of proposition 5

(i) $l_J = 1/\bar{p}$ if $p' = 0$, $l_J = 1$ if $p' = p$ and $l_J = 1/p$ if $p' = 1/p$. From lemma 1 follows that $Q_J = P_0^*$ if $p' = 0$, $Q_J = P$ if $p' = p$ and $Q_J = P_1^*$ if $p' = 1$.

(ii) If $l_f = l_J$, then $a'_f = a'_J$. Since $p' = p'_J = p'_f$ and $q' = q$, we obtain $Q_f = Q_J$.

We have the following consistency:

$$\begin{aligned} l_{KL} = l_H = l_{\chi^2} = l_{IKL} = l_J (= 1) & \quad \text{if } p' = p \\ l_{KL} = l_H = l_{\chi^2} = l_J (= 1/\bar{p}) & \quad \text{if } p' = 0 \\ l_{KL} = l_H = l_{\chi^2} = l_J (= 1/p) & \quad \text{if } p' = 1 \end{aligned}$$

Since $l_{IKL} = 1$ if $p' = 0$ respectively if $p' = 1$, Q obtained minimizing the IKL-divergence is not consistent with Jeffrey conditionalisation if $p' = 0$ respectively if $p' = 1$.

It remains to show $l_{KL} \neq l_J$, $l_H \neq l_J$, $l_{\chi^2} \neq l_J$ and $l_{IKL} \neq l_J$ for $p' \in (p, 1)$ respectively

for $p' \in (0, p)$. We do the proof for the KL-divergence. The following lines are equivalent:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{p'}{p} &= \left(\frac{p'}{p}\right)^{p'} \left(\frac{\bar{p}'}{\bar{p}}\right)^{\bar{p}'} \\
1 &= \left(\frac{p'}{p}\right)^{p'-1} \left(\frac{\bar{p}'}{\bar{p}}\right)^{\bar{p}'} \\
&= \left(\frac{p}{p'}\right)^{\bar{p}'} \left(\frac{\bar{p}'}{\bar{p}}\right)^{\bar{p}'} \\
&= \left(\frac{p}{p'} \cdot \frac{\bar{p}'}{\bar{p}}\right)^{\bar{p}'} \\
1 &= \frac{p}{\bar{p}} \cdot \frac{\bar{p}'}{p'} \\
\frac{\bar{p}}{p} &= \frac{\bar{p}'}{p'}
\end{aligned}$$

Clearly, there is no $p' \in (p, 1)$ which satisfies the latter equation. The proof for $p' \in (0, p)$ is similar. Hence $l_{KL} \neq l_J$ for $p' \in (0, p) \cup (p, 1)$.

A.10 Proof of proposition 6

Let Q be parametrized according to equations (4) and defined by Adams conditioning (c.f. equation (19)). Then $Q(B|A) = p'$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(A \wedge B) &= a'p' & Q(A \wedge \neg B) &= a'\bar{p}' \\
Q(\neg A \wedge B) &= \bar{a}'q' & Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) &= \bar{a}'\bar{q}'
\end{aligned}$$

By Adams conditioning we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(A \wedge B) &= 0 + P(A \wedge B|A \wedge B) \cdot Q(B|A) \cdot P(A) + 0 \\
&= Q(B|A) \cdot P(A) = p' a
\end{aligned}$$

Comparison with $Q(A \wedge B) = a'p'$ yields $a' = a$, i. e. $a' = a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot l)$ where $l = 1$.

We observe that Adams conditioning yields

$$Q(A \wedge \neg B) = 0 + 0 + Q(\neg B|A) \cdot P(A) = \bar{p}'a$$

and comparison with $Q(A \wedge \neg B) = a'\bar{p}'$ confirms that $a' = a$.

Adams conditioning yields further

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\neg A \wedge B) &= P(\neg A \wedge B | \neg A) \cdot P(\neg A) + 0 + 0 \\ &= P(\neg A \wedge B) / P(\neg A) \cdot P(\neg A) = P(\neg A \wedge B) = \bar{a}q \end{aligned}$$

and since $a' = a$, we obtain by comparison with $Q(\neg A \wedge B) = \bar{a}'q'$ that $q' = q$.

Last, we observe that Adams conditioning yields

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) &= P(\neg A \wedge \neg B | \neg A) \cdot P(\neg A) + 0 + 0 \\ &= P(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = \bar{q}\bar{a} \end{aligned}$$

which confirms in view of $Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = \bar{a}'\bar{q}'$ that $a' = a$ and $q' = q$.

A.11 Proof of proposition 7

Let $p'' = p$ and $q'' = q$. Then $\tilde{P} = P$ is equivalent to $a'' = a$. Hence, we have to show that $a'' = a$ iff $l(p') \cdot l'(p'') = 1$.

Note

$$\begin{aligned} a' &= \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l(p')} \\ \bar{a}' &= 1 - a' = \frac{\bar{a} \cdot l(p')}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l(p')} \end{aligned}$$

This gives

$$\begin{aligned} a'' &= \frac{a'}{a' + \bar{a}' \cdot l'(p'')} \\ &= \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l(p') \cdot l'(p'')} \end{aligned}$$

i. e. $a'' = a$ iff $l(p') \cdot l'(p) = 1$.

$l_J(p') = p'/p > 1$ and $l'_J(p'') = \bar{p}''/\bar{p}' = \bar{p}/\bar{p}' > 1$. Hence $l_J(p') \cdot l'_J(p) > 1$.

$l_{IKL} \equiv 1$ for any $p' \in [0, 1]$. Hence $l(p') \cdot l'(p) = 1$ for any $p' \in [0, 1]$.

$l_{KL}(p') \cdot l'_{KL}(p) \neq 1$ for instance if $p = 0.6$ and $p' = 0.8$ since $l_{KL}(0.8) \cdot l'_{KL}(0.6) \approx 1.22$.

$l_H(p') = l'_H(p)$. Hence $l_H(p') \cdot l'_H(p) = 1$ is equivalent to $l_H(p') = 1$. The latter is equivalent to $p' = p$.

$l_{\chi^2}(p') \cdot l'_{\chi^2}(p) \neq 1$ for instance if $p = 0.6$ and $p' = 0.8$ since $l_{\chi^2}(0.8) \cdot l'_{\chi^2}(0.6) \approx 1.46$.

A.12 Proof of proposition 8

Parametrise P and Q according to equations (1) and (4) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$ and $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$. According to proposition 3 Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$ yields $q' = q$ and $a' = a/(a + \bar{a} \cdot l)$ with $l = p'/p$.

(i) $Q(A) = a' = ap/(ap + \bar{a}p')$. Differentiating by p' yields

$$\frac{-ap}{(ap + \bar{a}p')^2} \bar{a} < 0.$$

Hence $Q(A)$ is a strictly monotone decreasing function of p' on $[0, 1]$.

$Q(A \wedge \neg B) = a'\bar{p}'$. Differentiating by p' yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{-ap}{(ap + \bar{a}p')^2} \bar{a}\bar{p}' + \frac{-ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'} &= \frac{-ap\bar{a}\bar{p}' - ap(ap + \bar{a}p')}{(ap + \bar{a}p')^2} \\ &= \frac{-ap(\bar{a}\bar{p}' + ap + \bar{a}p')}{(ap + \bar{a}p')^2} = \frac{-ap(\bar{a} + ap)}{(ap + \bar{a}p')^2} < 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $Q(A \wedge \neg B)$ is a strictly monotone decreasing function of p' on $[0, 1]$.

Since $Q = P$ if $p' = p$ and $Q = P_1^*$ if $p' = 1$ (c. f. proposition 5) the inequalities follow from above.

(ii) $Q(A \wedge B) = a'p'$. Differentiating by p' yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{-ap}{(ap + \bar{a}p')^2} \bar{a}p' + \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'} &= \frac{-ap\bar{a}p' + ap(ap + \bar{a}p')}{(ap + \bar{a}p')^2} \\ &= \frac{ap(-\bar{a}p' + ap + \bar{a}p')}{(ap + \bar{a}p')^2} = \frac{(ap)^2}{(ap + \bar{a}p')^2} > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $Q(A \wedge B)$ is strictly monotone increasing function of p' on $[0, 1]$.

$Q(\neg A \wedge B) = \bar{a}'q'$ and $Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = \bar{a}'\bar{q}'$ are strictly monotone increasing functions of p' on $[0, 1]$ since \bar{a}' is a strictly monotone increasing function of p' on $[0, 1]$.

$Q(B) = Q(A \wedge B) + Q(\neg A \wedge B)$ is a strictly monotone increasing function of p' on $[0, 1]$ since $Q(A \wedge B)$ and $Q(\neg A \wedge B)$ are strictly monotone increasing function of p' on $[0, 1]$.

Since $Q = P$ if $p' = p$ and $Q = P_1^*$ if $p' = 1$ (c. f. proposition 5) the inequalities follow from above.

A.13 Proof of lemma 4

$$(viii) P(A|B) = \frac{P(A \wedge B)}{P(B)} = \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}q} = \frac{\frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}}}{\frac{ap + \bar{a}q}{ap + \bar{a}}} = \frac{P_1^*(A \wedge B)}{P_1^*(B)} = P_1^*(A|B)$$

$$(vii) P(\neg A|B) = 1 - P(A|B) = 1 - P_1^*(A|B) = P_1^*(\neg A|B)$$

$$(vi) P(B|\neg A) = \frac{P(\neg A \wedge B)}{P(\neg A)} = \frac{\bar{a}q}{\bar{a}q + \bar{a}\bar{q}} = \frac{\frac{\bar{a}q}{ap + \bar{a}}}{\frac{\bar{a}q + \bar{a}\bar{q}}{ap + \bar{a}}} = \frac{P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B)}{P_1^*(\neg A)} = P_1^*(B|\neg A)$$

$$(v) P(\neg B|\neg A) = 1 - P(B|\neg A) = 1 - P_1^*(B|\neg A) = P_1^*(\neg B|\neg A)$$

$$(i) P(B|A) = \frac{P(A \wedge B)}{P(A)} = \frac{ap}{a} = p$$

$$P_1^*(B|A) = \frac{P_1^*(A \wedge B)}{P_1^*(A)} = \frac{P_1^*(A \wedge B)}{P_1^*(A \wedge B)} = 1$$

$$(ii) P(\neg B|A) = 1 - P(B|A) > 1 - P_1^*(B|A) = P_1^*(\neg B|A) = 0$$

$$(iii) P(A|\neg B) = \frac{P(A \wedge \neg B)}{P(\neg B)} = \frac{a\bar{p}}{a\bar{p} + \bar{a}\bar{q}}$$

$$P_1^*(A|\neg B) = \frac{P_1^*(A \wedge \neg B)}{P_1^*(\neg B)} = 0$$

$$(iv) P(\neg A|\neg B) = 1 - P(A|\neg B) < 1 - P_1^*(A|\neg B) = P_1^*(\neg A|\neg B)$$

A.14 Proof of proposition 9

(v) and (vi): From lemma 3 it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} Q(B|\neg A) &= \frac{Q(\neg A \wedge B)}{Q(\neg A)} \\ &= \frac{P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B)}{Q(\neg A)} \\ &= \frac{P_1^*(\neg A \wedge B)}{P_1^*(\neg A)} \cdot \frac{P_1^*(\neg A) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B)}{Q(\neg A)} \\ &= P_1^*(B|\neg A) \cdot \frac{Q(\neg A)}{Q(\neg A)} = P_1^*(B|\neg A) = P(B|\neg A) \end{aligned}$$

$$Q(\neg B|\neg A) = 1 - Q(B|\neg A) = 1 - P(B|\neg A) = P(\neg B|\neg A)$$

Note, an alternative proof is to parametrise P and Q according to equations (1) and

(4) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$ and $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$. Proposition 3 then gives $Q(B|\neg A) = q' = q = P(B|\neg A)$ and $Q(\neg B|\neg) = 1 - q' = 1 - q = P(\neg B|\neg A)$.

(vii) and (viii): From lemma 3 it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} Q(A|B) &= \frac{Q(A \wedge B)}{Q(B)} \\ &= \frac{P_1^*(A \wedge B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B)}{Q(B)} \\ &= \frac{P_1^*(A \wedge B)}{P_1^*(B)} \cdot \frac{P_1^*(B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B)}{Q(B)} \\ &= P_1^*(A|B) \cdot \frac{Q(B)}{Q(B)} = P_1^*(A|B) = P(A|B) \\ Q(\neg A|B) &= 1 - Q(A|B) = 1 - P(A|B) = P(\neg A|B) \end{aligned}$$

(i) and (ii): If $p' \in (p, 1]$, then

$$\begin{aligned} Q(B|A) &= p' > p = P(B|A) \\ Q(\neg B|A) &= 1 - p' < 1 - p = P(\neg B|A) \end{aligned}$$

(iii) and (iv): If $p' \in (p, 1]$, then from proposition 8 follows that

$$Q(\neg B) = 1 - Q(B) < 1 - P(B) = P(\neg B)$$

and the proposition states that $Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) > P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\neg A|\neg B) &= \frac{Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B)}{Q(\neg B)} > \frac{P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)}{P(\neg B)} = P(\neg A|\neg B) \\ Q(A|\neg B) &= 1 - Q(\neg A|\neg B) < 1 - P(\neg A|\neg B) = P(A|\neg B) \end{aligned}$$

A.15 Proof of proposition 10

Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B and parametrized according to equations (1) and (4) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$ and $0 \leq a', p', q' \leq 1$ and let Q be defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$, i. e. $Q(\cdot) := P(\cdot|\neg A \vee B) Q(\neg A \vee B) + P(\cdot|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B))$ and $p' = Q(B|A) > p$.

Let further \tilde{P} denote the probability distribution which is defined over the propositional variables $\tilde{A} := \neg B$ and $\tilde{B} := \neg A$ by $\tilde{P}(\tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) := P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$, $\tilde{P}(\tilde{A} \wedge \neg \tilde{B}) := P(A \wedge \neg B)$, $\tilde{P}(\neg \tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) := P(\neg A \wedge B)$ and $\tilde{P}(\neg \tilde{A} \wedge \neg \tilde{B}) := P(A \wedge B)$. Let \tilde{P} be parametrized according to equations (1) with parameters $0 < \tilde{a}, \tilde{p}, \tilde{q} < 1$.

Let further \tilde{Q} denote the probability distribution which is defined over the propositional variables \tilde{A} and \tilde{B} and parametrized according to equations (4) with parameters $0 \leq \tilde{a}', \tilde{p}', \tilde{q}' \leq 1$ and let \tilde{Q} be defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg\tilde{A} \vee \tilde{B}$, i. e. $\tilde{Q}(\cdot) := \tilde{P}(\cdot | \neg\tilde{A} \vee \tilde{B}) \tilde{Q}(\neg\tilde{A} \vee \tilde{B}) + \tilde{P}(\cdot | \neg(\neg\tilde{A} \vee \tilde{B})) \tilde{Q}(\neg(\neg\tilde{A} \vee \tilde{B}))$ and $\tilde{p} = \tilde{Q}(\tilde{B} | \tilde{A}) = Q(\neg A | \neg B)$.

We define

$$\begin{aligned} s_1 &:= ap = P(A \wedge B) = \tilde{P}(\neg\tilde{A} \wedge \neg\tilde{B}) = \tilde{a}\tilde{q} \\ s_2 &:= a\bar{p} = P(A \wedge \neg B) = \tilde{P}(\tilde{A} \wedge \neg\tilde{B}) = \tilde{a}\tilde{p} \\ s_3 &:= \bar{a}q = P(\neg A \wedge B) = \tilde{P}(\neg\tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) = \tilde{a}\tilde{q} \\ s_4 &:= \bar{a}\bar{q} = P(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = \tilde{P}(\tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) = \tilde{a}\tilde{p} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} s'_1 &:= Q(A \wedge B) \\ s'_2 &:= Q(A \wedge \neg B) \\ s'_3 &:= Q(\neg A \wedge B) \\ s'_4 &:= Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B). \end{aligned}$$

The task is now to show that

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{Q}(\tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) &= s'_4 \\ \tilde{Q}(\tilde{A} \wedge \neg\tilde{B}) &= s'_2 \\ \tilde{Q}(\neg\tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) &= s'_3 \\ \tilde{Q}(\neg\tilde{A} \wedge \neg\tilde{B}) &= s'_1 \end{aligned}$$

Before we start, note the following:

$$\begin{aligned} s'_1 &= a'p' = \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'} \cdot p' = \frac{s_1}{ap + \bar{a}p'} \cdot p' \\ s'_3 &= \bar{a}'q' = \frac{\bar{a}p'}{ap + \bar{a}p'} \cdot q' = \frac{s_3}{ap + \bar{a}p'} \cdot p' \\ s'_4 &= \bar{a}'\bar{q}' = \frac{\bar{a}p'}{ap + \bar{a}p'} \cdot \bar{q}' = \frac{s_4}{ap + \bar{a}p'} \cdot p' \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\frac{s'_1}{s_1} = \frac{s'_3}{s_3} = \frac{s'_4}{s_4} \quad (29)$$

and

$$\frac{s'_4}{s'_1 + s'_3} = \frac{s_4}{s_1 + s_3}. \quad (30)$$

Note further

$$\tilde{a}' = \frac{\tilde{a}\tilde{p}}{\tilde{a}\tilde{p} + \tilde{a}'\tilde{p}'} = \frac{s_4}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'}, \quad (31)$$

$$\tilde{a}' = \frac{(s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'}, \quad (32)$$

$$\tilde{q}' = \tilde{q} = \tilde{P}(\tilde{B}|\neg\tilde{A}) = \frac{s_3}{s_1 + s_3}, \quad (33)$$

$$\tilde{q}' = \frac{s_1}{s_1 + s_3}, \quad (34)$$

and

$$\tilde{p}' = Q(\neg A|\neg B) = \frac{s'_4}{s'_2 + s'_4}. \quad (35)$$

We start with the proof of $\tilde{Q}(\tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) = s'_4$:

From equations (31) and (35) follows

$$\tilde{Q}(\tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) = \tilde{a}'\tilde{p}' = \frac{s_4}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'} \cdot \frac{s'_4}{s'_2 + s'_4}.$$

Hence we need to show that

$$s'_4 = \frac{s_4}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'} \cdot \frac{s'_4}{s'_2 + s'_4}.$$

which is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= \frac{s_4}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'} \cdot \frac{1}{s'_2 + s'_4} \\ \frac{s_4}{s'_2 + s'_4} &= s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \frac{s'_4}{s'_2 + s'_4} \\ s_4 &= (s'_2 + s'_4) \cdot s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot s'_4 \\ s_4 \cdot (1 - s'_2 - s'_4) &= (s_1 + s_3)s'_4 \\ s_4(s'_1 + s'_3) &= (s_1 + s_3) \cdot s'_4 \\ \frac{s_4}{s_1 + s_3} &= \frac{s'_4}{s'_1 + s'_3}. \end{aligned}$$

Equation (30) completes the proof.

Next, we prove that $\tilde{Q}(\neg\tilde{A} \wedge \neg\tilde{B}) = s'_1$. From equations (32) and (34) follows that

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{Q}(\neg\tilde{A} \wedge \neg\tilde{B}) &= \tilde{a}'\tilde{q}' = \frac{(s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'} \cdot \frac{s_1}{s_1 + s_3} \\ &= \frac{s_1 \cdot \tilde{p}'}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'}.\end{aligned}$$

Hence, we need to show that

$$\frac{s'_1}{s_1} = \frac{\tilde{p}'}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'}.$$

From equation (35) follows that

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\tilde{p}'}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'} &= \frac{\frac{s'_4}{s'_2 + s'_4}}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \frac{s'_4}{s'_2 + s'_4}} \\ &= \frac{s'_4}{s_4 \cdot (s'_2 + s'_4) + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot s'_4} \\ &= \frac{s'_4}{s_4 \cdot (1 - s'_1 + s'_3) + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot s'_4}\end{aligned}$$

and equation (30) gives

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\tilde{p}'}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'} &= \frac{s'_4}{s_4 \cdot (1 - s'_1 + s'_3) + (s'_1 + s'_3) \cdot s_4} \\ &= \frac{s'_4}{s_4}.\end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\frac{s'_1}{s_1} = \frac{s'_4}{s_4}$$

and equation (29) completes the proof.

Next, we prove that $\tilde{Q}(\neg\tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) = s'_3$. From equations (32) and (33) follows that

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{Q}(\neg\tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) &= \tilde{a}'\tilde{q}' = \frac{(s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'} \cdot \frac{s_3}{s_1 + s_3} \\ &= \frac{s_3 \cdot \tilde{p}'}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'}\end{aligned}$$

Hence, we need to show that

$$\frac{s'_3}{s_3} = \frac{\tilde{p}'}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'}$$

From equations (35) and (30) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\tilde{p}'}{s_4 + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot \tilde{p}'} &= \frac{s'_4}{s_4 \cdot (s'_2 + s'_4) + (s_1 + s_3) \cdot s'_4} \\ &= \frac{s'_4}{s_4 \cdot (1 - s'_1 + s'_3) + (s'_1 + s'_3) \cdot s_4} \\ &= \frac{s'_4}{s_4} \end{aligned}$$

and in view of equation (29) the proof is completed.

The proof of $\tilde{Q}(\tilde{A} \wedge \neg \tilde{B}) = s'_2$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{Q}(\tilde{A} \wedge \neg \tilde{B}) &= 1 - \tilde{Q}(\tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) - \tilde{Q}(\neg \tilde{A} \wedge \tilde{B}) - \tilde{Q}(\neg \tilde{A} \wedge \neg \tilde{B}) \\ &= 1 - s'_4 - s'_3 - s'_1 \\ &= s'_2 \end{aligned}$$

A.16 Proof of proposition 11

We assume that Q_1, \dots, Q_8 are parametrized according to equations (4) by parameters $a'_i, p'_i, q'_i, i = 1, \dots, 8$. We need to show that $a'_i = a'$, $p'_i = p'$ and $q'_i = q'$ for $i = 1, \dots, 8$.

Q, Q_1, \dots, Q_8 are defined by Jeffrey conditionalisation on $\neg A \vee B$. Hence proposition 3 gives $q' = q'_i = q$ and

$$a' = \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'} \quad , \quad a'_i = \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'_i}$$

for $i = 1, \dots, 8$.

Since $q' = q = q'_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, 8$, and since $a'_i = a'$ in case that $p'_i = p'$, it remains to show that $p'_i = p'$ for $i = 1, \dots, 8$.

1) $i = 1$, i. e. the constraint is $Q_1(A \wedge B) = Q(A \wedge B)$:

We define $c := P^*(A \wedge B) = ap/(ap + \bar{a})$. From lemma 3 it follows that

$$Q_1(A \wedge B) = a'_1 p'_1 = c \cdot (1 - a'_1 \bar{p}'_1)$$

which is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} a'_1 &= \frac{c}{p'_1 + c \bar{p}'_1} = \frac{ap}{p'_1(ap + \bar{a}) + ap(1 - p'_1)} \\ &= \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'_1} \end{aligned}$$

The constraint $Q_1(A \wedge B) = Q(A \wedge B)$ gives $a'_1 p'_1 = a' p'$ or equivalently $a'_1 = a' \cdot p' / p'_1$. Then it follows that

$$\frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'_1} = \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'} \cdot p' / p'_1$$

or equivalently

$$\begin{aligned} (ap + \bar{a}p') \cdot \frac{p'_1}{p'} &= ap + \bar{a}p'_1 \\ \left(\frac{ap}{p'} + \bar{a}\right) \cdot p'_1 &= ap + \bar{a}p'_1 \\ \frac{ap}{p'} \cdot p'_1 &= ap \\ p'_1 &= p' \end{aligned}$$

2) $i = 2$, i. e. the constraint is $Q_2(A \wedge \neg B) = Q(A \wedge \neg B)$:

The constraint gives $a'_2 \bar{p}'_2 = a' \bar{p}'$ and proposition 3 gives $a'_2 = ap / (ap + \bar{a}p'_2)$. The following lines are equivalent:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'_2} \cdot \bar{p}'_2 &= \frac{ap}{ap + \bar{a}p'} \cdot \bar{p}' \\ (1 - p'_2)(ap + \bar{a}p') &= (1 - p')(ap + \bar{a}p'_2) \\ ap + \bar{a}p' - app'_2 - \bar{a}p'p'_2 &= ap + \bar{a}p'_2 - app' - \bar{a}p'_2p' \\ p' - ap' - app'_2 - p'p'_2 + ap'p'_2 &= p'_2 - ap'_2 - app' - p'_2p' + ap'p'_2 \\ p'_2(-ap - p' + ap' - 1 + a + p' - ap') &= -p' + ap' - app' \\ p'_2(-ap - 1 + a) &= p'(-ap - 1 + a) \\ p'_2 &= p' \end{aligned}$$

3) $i = 3$, i. e. the constraint is $Q_3(\neg A \wedge B) = Q(\neg A \wedge B)$:

From $Q_3(\neg A \wedge B) = \bar{a}'_3 q'_3 = \bar{a}' q' = Q(\neg A \wedge B)$ and $q'_3 = q'$ it follows that $a'_3 = a'$.

From $a'_3 = a'$, $q'_3 = q'$ and $Q_3(\neg A \wedge B) = P^*(\neg A \wedge B) \cdot Q_3(\neg A \vee B)$ (c. f. lemma 3) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} Q_3(\neg A \wedge B) &= \bar{a}'q' = Q(\neg A \wedge B) = P^*(\neg A \wedge B) \cdot (1 - a'\bar{p}') \\ &= \bar{a}'_3 q'_3 = Q_3(\neg A \wedge B) = P^*(\neg A \wedge B) \cdot (1 - a'_3 \bar{p}'_3). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $p'_3 = p'$.

4) $i = 4$, i. e. the constraint is $Q_4(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$:

From $Q_4(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = \bar{a}'_4 \bar{q}'_4 = \bar{a}' \bar{q}' = Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$ and $q'_4 = q'$ it follows that $a'_4 = a'$.

From $a'_4 = a'$, $q'_4 = q'$ and $Q_4(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = P^*(\neg A \wedge \neg B) \cdot Q_4(\neg A \vee B)$ (c. f. lemma 3) it follows that $p'_4 = p'$.

5) $i = 5$, i. e. the constraint is $Q_5(B|A) = Q(B|A)$, i. e. $p'_5 = p'$.

6) $i = 6$, i. e. the constraint is $Q_6(\neg B|A) = Q(\neg B|A)$, i. e. $p'_6 = p'$ since $Q_6(\neg B|A) = 1 - p'_6$ and $Q(\neg B|A) = 1 - p'$.

7) $i = 7$, i. e. the constraint is $Q_7(\neg A|\neg B) = Q(\neg A|\neg B)$

Note,

$$Q(\neg A|\neg B) = \frac{\bar{a}'\bar{q}'}{a'\bar{p}' + \bar{a}'\bar{q}'} = \frac{\bar{q}}{a'/\bar{a}' \cdot \bar{p}' + \bar{q}}$$

$$Q_7(\neg A|\neg B) = \frac{\bar{a}'_7\bar{q}'_7}{a'_7\bar{p}'_7 + \bar{a}'_7\bar{q}'_7} = \frac{\bar{q}}{a'_7/\bar{a}'_7 \cdot \bar{p}'_7 + \bar{q}}$$

Hence $Q_7(\neg A|\neg B) = Q(\neg A|\neg B)$ is equivalent to

$$a'/\bar{a}' \cdot \bar{p}' = a'_7/\bar{a}'_7 \cdot \bar{p}'_7. \quad (36)$$

Since

$$\frac{a'}{\bar{a}'} = \frac{a}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l} / \frac{\bar{a} \cdot l}{a + \bar{a} \cdot l} = \frac{a}{\bar{a} \cdot l}$$

where $l = p'/p$ and similarly

$$\frac{a'_7}{\bar{a}'_7} = \frac{a_7}{\bar{a}_7 \cdot l_7}$$

where $l_7 = p'_7/p_7$ equation (36) is equivalent to

$$\frac{a}{\bar{a} \cdot l} \cdot \bar{p}' = \frac{a}{\bar{a} \cdot l_7} \cdot \bar{p}'_7$$

i. e.

$$\frac{\bar{p}'}{p'/p} = \frac{\bar{p}'_7}{p_7/p}$$

respectively

$$\frac{\bar{p}'}{p'} = \frac{\bar{p}'_7}{p_7}$$

and the latter is equivalent to $p'_7 = p'$.

8) $i = 8$, i. e. the constraint is $Q_8(A|\neg B) = Q(A|\neg B)$

Since $Q_8(\neg A|\neg B) = 1 - Q_8(A|\neg B) = 1 - Q(A|\neg B) = Q(\neg A|\neg B)$, we obtain $Q_8(\neg A|\neg B) = Q(\neg A|\neg B)$. From case $i = 7$, then follows $p'_8 = p'$.

B Parameter determination

Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . The probability distributions P is parametrized according to equations (1) with parameters $0 < a, p, q < 1$. Q is for instance obtained by minimizing a f -divergence between P and Q . The question is whether there exists a propositional variable C such that Q is consistent with Jeffrey conditionalisation on C , i. e. whether there exists a propositional variable C which satisfies

$$Q(\cdot) = P(\cdot|C) Q(C) + P(\cdot|\neg C) Q(\neg C) \quad (37)$$

given P and given Q .

In this section we want to point out how C can be determined if C exists. Let us introduce for this purpose the following parametrizations of P and Q :

A	B	C	P	Q
1	1	1	p_1	q_1
1	1	0	p_2	q_2
1	0	1	p_3	q_3
1	0	0	p_4	q_4
0	1	1	p_5	q_5
0	1	0	p_6	q_6
0	0	1	p_7	q_7
0	0	0	p_8	q_8

$P(A \wedge B)$, $P(A \wedge \neg B)$, $P(\neg A \wedge B)$ and $P(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$ respectively $Q(A \wedge B)$, $Q(A \wedge \neg B)$, $Q(\neg A \wedge B)$ and $Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$ are given. Hence, the parameters have to satisfy the following conditions:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
P(A \wedge B) = p_1 + p_2 & Q(A \wedge B) = q_1 + q_2 \\
P(A \wedge \neg B) = p_3 + p_4 & Q(A \wedge \neg B) = q_3 + q_4 \\
P(\neg A \wedge B) = p_5 + p_6 & Q(\neg A \wedge B) = q_5 + q_6 \\
P(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = p_7 + p_8 & Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = q_7 + q_8
\end{array}$$

$$p_i \geq 0 \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, 8 \quad , \quad q_i \geq 0 \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, 8$$

and in addition we have to require that

$$\begin{array}{l}
P(C) = p_1 + p_3 + p_5 + p_7 > 0 \\
P(\neg C) = p_2 + p_4 + p_6 + p_8 > 0
\end{array}$$

The latter guarantees that the conditional probabilities $P(\cdot|C)$ and $P(\cdot|\neg C)$ are defined.

Jeffrey conditionalisation on C is defined in equation (37). Hence, Q is consistent with Jeffrey conditionalisation on C if the parameters p_i and q_i , $i = 1, \dots, 8$, satisfy

$$\begin{array}{l}
Q(A \wedge B) = p_{1/1357} \cdot q_{1357} + p_{2/2468} \cdot q_{2468} \\
Q(A \wedge \neg B) = p_{3/1357} \cdot q_{1357} + p_{4/2468} \cdot q_{2468} \\
Q(\neg A \wedge B) = p_{5/1357} \cdot q_{1357} + p_{6/2468} \cdot q_{2468} \\
Q(\neg A \wedge \neg B) = p_{7/1357} \cdot q_{1357} + p_{8/2468} \cdot q_{2468}
\end{array}$$

where $q_{1357} := q_1 + q_3 + q_5 + q_7$, $q_{2468} := q_2 + q_4 + q_6 + q_8$ and $p_{1/1357} = p_1/(p_1 + p_3 + p_5 + p_7)$ etc.

It is unclear for us, whether there exist in general or under some conditions (which?) parameters p_i and q_i , $i = 1, \dots, 8$ which satisfy the conditions presented above.

C Adams conditioning

In this section we explain how the formula (19) for Adams conditioning can be derived. For further information, we refer to Bradley (2005) and Douven and Romeijn (2011).

Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables H and E . Assume $0 < P(E) < 1$. Then probabilistic expansion yields

$$\begin{aligned}
P(H) &= P(H \wedge E) + P(H \wedge \neg E) \\
&= P(H|E) \cdot P(E) + P(H|\neg E) \cdot P(\neg E)
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

An agent who learns that the probability of E is not $P(E)$ but $Q(E)$ and updates by Jeffrey conditionalisation, simply replaces $P(E)$ by $Q(E)$ and $P(\neg E)$ by $Q(\neg E)$ in (38):

$$Q(H) = P(H|E) \cdot Q(E) + P(H|\neg E) \cdot Q(\neg E)$$

An agent who learns that the conditional probability of H given E is not $P(H|E)$ but $Q(H|E)$ and updates by Adams conditioning, simply replaces $P(H|E)$ by $Q(H|E)$ and $P(H|\neg E)$ by $Q(H|\neg E)$ in (38):

$$Q(H) = Q(H|E) \cdot P(E) + Q(H|\neg E) \cdot P(\neg E)$$

The above can be generalized: Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables H , E_1 and E_2 with $0 < P(E_1 \wedge E_2), P(E_1 \wedge \neg E_2), P(\neg E_1 \wedge E_2), P(\neg E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) < 1$. Then probabilistic expansion yields

$$\begin{aligned}
P(H) &= P(H \wedge (E_1 \wedge E_2)) \\
&\quad + P(H \wedge (E_1 \wedge \neg E_2)) \\
&\quad + P(H \wedge (\neg E_1 \wedge E_2)) \\
&\quad + P(H \wedge (\neg E_1 \wedge \neg E_2)) \\
&= P(H|E_1 \wedge E_2) \cdot P(E_1 \wedge E_2) \\
&\quad + P(H|E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \cdot P(E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \\
&\quad + P(H|\neg E_1 \wedge E_2) \cdot P(\neg E_1 \wedge E_2) \\
&\quad + P(H|\neg E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \cdot P(\neg E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \\
&= P(H|E_1 \wedge E_2) \cdot P(E_2|E_1) \cdot P(E_1) \\
&\quad + P(H|E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \cdot P(\neg E_2|E_1) \cdot P(E_1) \\
&\quad + P(H|\neg E_1 \wedge E_2) \cdot P(E_2|\neg E_1) \cdot P(\neg E_1) \\
&\quad + P(H|\neg E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \cdot P(\neg E_2|\neg E_1) \cdot P(\neg E_1)
\end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

Note, we can equally expand to

$$\begin{aligned}
P(H) &= P(H|E_1 \wedge E_2) \cdot P(E_1|E_2) \cdot P(E_2) \\
&\quad + P(H|E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \cdot P(\neg E_1|E_2) \cdot P(E_2) \\
&\quad + P(H|\neg E_1 \wedge E_2) \cdot P(E_1|\neg E_2) \cdot P(\neg E_2) \\
&\quad + P(H|\neg E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \cdot P(\neg E_1|\neg E_2) \cdot P(\neg E_2)
\end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

If the agent learns that the probability of E_1 is not $P(E_1)$ but $Q(E_1)$, then the agent updates by Jeffrey conditionalisation on E_1 , i. e. she replaces $P(E_1)$ respectively $P(\neg E_1)$ in equation (39) by $Q(E_1)$ respectively $Q(\neg E_1)$ and obtains

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(H) &= P(H|E_1 \wedge E_2) \cdot P(E_2|E_1) \cdot Q(E_1) \\
&\quad + P(H|E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \cdot P(\neg E_2|E_1) \cdot Q(E_1) \\
&\quad + P(H|\neg E_1 \wedge E_2) \cdot P(E_2|\neg E_1) \cdot Q(\neg E_1) \\
&\quad + P(H|\neg E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \cdot P(\neg E_2|\neg E_1) \cdot Q(\neg E_1)
\end{aligned}$$

Likewise, if the agent learns that the probability of E_2 is not $P(E_2)$ but $Q(E_2)$, then she replaces $P(E_2)$ and $P(\neg E_2)$ in equation (40) by $Q(E_2)$ and $Q(\neg E_2)$.

If the agent learns however that the probability of E_2 given E_1 is not $P(E_2|E_1)$ but $Q(E_2|E_1)$, then the agent updates by Adams conditioning and replaces $P(E_2|E_1)$ respectively $P(\neg E_2|E_1)$ in equation (39) by $Q(E_2|E_1)$ respectively $Q(\neg E_2|E_1)$ and obtains

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(H) &= P(H|E_1 \wedge E_2) \cdot Q(E_2|E_1) \cdot P(E_1) \\
&\quad + P(H|E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \cdot Q(\neg E_2|E_1) \cdot P(E_1) \\
&\quad + P(H|\neg E_1 \wedge E_2) \cdot P(E_2|\neg E_1) \cdot P(\neg E_1) \\
&\quad + P(H|\neg E_1 \wedge \neg E_2) \cdot P(\neg E_2|\neg E_1) \cdot P(\neg E_1)
\end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

Likewise, if the agent learns that the probability of E_1 given E_2 is not $P(E_1|E_2)$ but $Q(E_1|E_2)$, then the agent updates by Adams conditioning and replaces $P(E_1|E_2)$ respectively $P(\neg E_1|E_2)$ in equation (40) by $Q(E_1|E_2)$ respectively $Q(\neg E_1|E_2)$. The agent has to do similiar replacement if she learns that the probability of E_2 given $\neg E_1$ is not $P(E_2|\neg E_1)$ but $Q(E_2|\neg E_1)$, respectively that the probability of E_1 given $\neg E_2$ is not $P(E_1|\neg E_2)$ but $Q(E_1|\neg E_2)$

Now, the formula given in equation (19) for Adams conditioning is simply obtained by identifying E_1 with A and E_2 with B in equation (41) and de-expanding the third and the fourth term. Doing this and replacing H by a spareholder, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\cdot) &= P(\cdot|A \wedge B) \cdot Q(B|A) \cdot P(A) \\ &\quad + P(\cdot|A \wedge \neg B) \cdot Q(\neg B|A) \cdot P(A) \\ &\quad + P(\cdot|\neg A) \cdot P(\neg A) \end{aligned}$$

which is identical to equation (19).

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